

THOT THEORY OF TONE

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Jamsay Dogon. Analytical report on the tonal system

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0. This analytical report follows Questionnaire version 8d. It is primarily based on (Heath 2008), taking into account subsequent work by the same author. I am greatly indebted to Jeffrey Heath for his helpful answers to my questions, his comments on the pre-final draft, and for sharing yet unpublished Jamsay data with me. Any mistakes and misinterpretations are my sole responsibility.

1. General information about the language

1.1. Language name

Jamsay, Diamsay.
ISO-639: djm, Glottolog: jams1239.

1.2. Genetic affiliation and distribution

Plains Dogon (< Eastern Dogon) < Dogon.
Geographic area: SE Mali, probably also across Burkina Faso border.
Number of speakers: over 30k. (estim. 2008).

1.3. Dialects

A distinct dialect of Gourou is spoken in the region of Koro; otherwise dialectal differentiation has not been studied seriously. Heath's data come chiefly from the Douentza area.

1.4. Relevant publications

The only academic treatise of Jamsay predating Heath's fieldwork is a relatively hard-to-obtain dissertation (Ongoïba 1988). Heath (2008: 5, 722) mentions this study, but never cites it. (Heath & McPherson 2013; McPherson 2014; McPherson & Heath 2016) are works on intragenetic typology of tone in Dogon, drawing on data from Jamsay among other languages of the family. The diachrony of tone is addressed in (Heath 2020) with special emphasis on Jamsay and in (Heath 2022) in a broader Dogon perspective.

2. Segmental phonology

2.1. Phonemic inventory

2.1.1. Vowels

2.1.1.1. Vowel inventory

Short Oral		Long Oral		Nasalized	
i	u	i:	u:	i: ⁿ	u: ⁿ
e	o	e:	o:	ε: ⁿ	o: ⁿ
ε	ɔ	ε:	ɔ:		
	a		a:		a: ⁿ

Table 1. Jamsay vowels

Three series of vowels are distinguished in Jamsay: short, long, and nasalized (Heath 2008: 40).

Vowel length is contrastive, cf. *yòrɔ́*- ‘be soft’ vs. *yò:rɔ́*- ‘cook on fire’. There are positional constraints on the distribution of long vs. short vowels: long vowels in non-initial syllables are absent in verbs stems and uncommon in stems of other word classes. Monosyllabic verb stems always contain a syllable with a long vowel; monosyllabic noun stems may contain a short vowel, but still should be at least bimoraic. In addition, stem-final short vowels can be lengthened to accommodate a tone contour (see §6.2.1 Contour-Tone Mora-Addition below). However, one would be wrong to assume that vowel length is only contrastive in initial (or even non-final) syllables. Among disyllabic noun stems all four possible combinations of long vs. short vowels are attested, cf. *béré* ‘stick’, *bùtò*: ‘Mitragyna tree’, *bè:rú* ‘nightjar’, *pù:-pá*: ‘blacksmith’s bellows’. Trisyllabic noun stems demonstrate 6 out of a 8 possible patterns (all except (C)VCV:CV: and (C)V:CVCV:).

A final long vowel can in principle bear a level tone, cf. *bàlpó*: ‘calabash drum’, *ilá*: ‘who?’, so length can not be explained by the demand to accommodate a tone contour.

There are also extra-long (trimoraic) vowels, but they only arise through Contour-Tone Mora-Addition in order to accommodate a tripartite tone contour and do not have a phonological status.

Nasalized vowels in lexical stems are phonetically long, which is reflected in the transcription. They form a five- rather than seven-vowel system, as e^n and o^n do not exist as independent phonemes.

However, in addition to phonological nasalization, there is phonetic nasalization of oral vowels triggered by an adjacent nasal (or nasalized) consonant, cf. *si.ⁿlé* ‘disease’ vs. *ji-jéwⁿé* [dʒídʒéwⁿé] ‘mud dauber wasp’. As can be seen from the latter word, this “redundant” nasalization doesn’t trigger neutralization in either length or height. Short nasalized vowels may also arise when a vowel-shortening process is applied to a nasalized vowel, e.g. in the formation of verbal nouns from monosyllabic stems (see §7.1.2.3 for details), cf. *jǎ.ⁿ* ‘dig’ : *jǎⁿ-yⁿ* ‘digging’. They are also attested outside stems, e.g. in the definite determiner *kùⁿ*¹ and in interjections like *ǎⁿhǎⁿ* ‘uh-huh!’. This may speak for recognizing them as a separate vowel series.

2.1.1.2. The status of long vowels

Long vowels are monophonemic. One argument in favour of this is provided by the process of **g-Spirantization** (Heath 2008: 31–33), under which initial *g* of the second syllable turns into y^2 between low back vowels:

$$(1) \quad g \rightarrow y / \#C \left\{ \begin{array}{l} a(:) \\ \text{ɔ}(:) \end{array} \right\} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} a \\ \text{ɔ} \end{array} \right\}$$

Thus, we find *y* in *dàyá*- ‘leave’, but not in its verbal noun *dàg-ú* ‘leave-NMR’ (where the potential target is followed by a high vowel), nor in *dǎrǎgǎ*- ‘ransomv’ (where it is in the third, rather than the second, syllable). However, g-Spirantization works regardless of the vowel length in the first syllable, thus besides *dàyá*- ‘leave’ we have *dà:yá* ‘night’. If long vowels were biphonemic, one would expect the latter form not to undergo spirantization, as it would have the structure **dà.à.gá*, with the velar in the third syllable.

¹ That *kùⁿ* is not phonologically a stem is also seen from the fact that it violates the constraint against all-L stems.

Another unit that is transcribed with a short nasalized vowel is the intensifier *èjⁿ* ⇒ ‘very’, but it is characterized by an exaggerated prolongation of the final vowel (see §3.2.3.1 below), so the vowel quantity may be hard to ascertain.

² This is a phonetic rather than a phonological process, with *y* being an allophone of *g*. However, Heath (2008: 32–33) reports cases of analogy-driven blocking of g-Spirantization that point at an incipient phonemicization of the *g/y* opposition. For this reason, *y* is consistently marked even in the phonological transcription.

2.1.2. Consonants

2.1.2.1. Consonant inventory³

	Labial	Alveolar	Alveopalatal	Velar	Laryngeal
Aspirated voiceless stops	p	t	c [tʃ]	k	
Voiced stops	b	d	j [dʒ]	g	
Nasals	m	n	ɲ [ɲ]	ŋ	
Voiceless fricatives	(f)	s	((š)) [ʃ]		
Laterals		l			
Oral sonorants	w	r	y		
Nasal sonorants	wⁿ	rⁿ	yⁿ		
Laryngeals					(h), ((ʔ))

Table 2. Jamsay consonants (after (Heath 2008: 30))

2.1.2.2. Consonant alternations

Like vowels, sonorants acquire the nasal feature from adjacent segments (Nasalization Spreading, see (Heath 2008: 48–49) for details). Cf. *páyá-rá-* tie-REV- ‘untie’ vs. *náŋá-rⁿá-* forget-REV- ‘remember’. Unlike in the case of vowels, this superficial nasalization is reflected in the transcription.

2.1.2.3. Interaction between consonants and tones

Synchronically, consonants do not seem to have any impact on the realization of tones. A syllable with a voiced onset can bear any tone. However, **in verbal lexicon** there is a correlation between the initial consonant and the tonal pattern of the stem (Heath 2008: 84–85). An initial voiceless stop, voiceless fricative, or liquid *l* is a nearly absolute predictor of an all-H pattern, which is also favored by stems with no initial consonant. On the contrary, initial voiced stops, semivowels, and, to a lesser extent, nasals statistically favor an LH pattern. No such correlations hold for parts of speech other than verbs (for more details on tonal patterns of verbs and other word classes see below in §4.2).

Consonant quality does not affect the limits of tonal spans.

2.2. Prosodic units

2.2.1. Syllable and mora

Most syllables are of the type CV or CV:. Closed syllables CVC, CV:C are also attested. Extra-heavy CV:: can only occur word-finally and only as a result of Tone-Contour Mora Addition.

Onsetless syllables (V, V:, VC, V:C, V::⁴) can be found in the word-initial position.

Only function words (e.g.) can be monomoraic. Stems of content words necessarily contain at least two morae, which provides non-tonal evidence, however subtle, for the contrast between light and heavy syllables.

All contour tones are analyzable as sequences of level tone components, with each such component linked to its own mora(e) (Heath 2008: 81). Possible tones for different syllable types are summarized in Table 3:

³ Consonantal segments given in parentheses are associated with loanwords. Those in double parentheses are marginal, confined to a few loanwords and/or semi-linguistic interjections.

⁴ Likely only attested in the form *é::-Ø* see.IPFV.L, from *é:-* ‘see’ (incorrectly given as *é:-* in the grammar; Jeffrey Heath, p.c.).

Syllable type	Mora count	Available tones / contours
(C)V	μ	L, H
(C)V:, (C)VC	μ μ	L, H, LH, HL
CV::, (C)V:C	μ μ μ	L, H, LH, HL, LHL

Table 3. Available tones/contours for syllable types

The TBU is thus a mora (although specific rules of tonal association can make reference to either syllable or mora, depending on the conditions, cf. 6.1.1).

2.2.2. Foot

There seem to be no reason to postulate a prosodic foot in Jamsay.

However, a number of phonological and phonetic processes point to an embryonic metrical structure that involves a stem-initial disyllabic foot (Heath 2008: 26–28ff). This foot is trochaic, in the sense that σ_2 behaves as a weak syllable as compared to the preceding σ_1 (and possibly the subsequent σ_3), being targeted by rules that involve consonantal and vocalic lenitions, including vowel deletion (there is no stress in Jamsay).

One relevant process is **g-Spirantization**, discussed above in connection with the status of long vowels. Other processes sensitive to the embryonic metrical structure are **Post-Sonorant Syncope** (§6.2.2), **Suffixal u-Apocope** (§6.2.3), **Inter-Word u-Apocope** (§6.2.4), **Verbal Noun V₂-Lenition** (Heath 2008: 62–63), and **Presuffixal V₂-Raising** (Heath 2008: 55–56). The latter two rules change vowel quality without any effect on the realization of tonemes and so are not covered in detail in the present analytical report.

There is also a slight non-contrastive pitch drop on V₂ of $\sigma\sigma$ - σ ... nominal compounds, especially with the HHHL tone pattern, which can also be linked to the embryonic trochaic metrical structure. This is described as an impressionistic finding requiring a further instrumental study (Heath 2008: 28).

The above-listed rules are rather divergent, not pointing to any uniform well-defined metrical structure. Some strictly target σ_2 , while others are extended to immediately following syllables; most are constrained to verb stems or their suffixal derivatives. There is no clear evidence for any metrical structure beyond the second syllable in longer words.

2.2.3. Word

There is no explicit discussion of wordhood criteria for Jamsay in (Heath 2008). The present analytical report follows word segmentation adopted in this grammar.

3. Tonal inventory

3.1. Character of the tonal system

The Jamsay tone system is level-based. Contour tones are transparently analyzable as sequences of level tone components.

3.1.1. If it is a (predominantly) level-tone system, how many levels does it count?

There are two levels: H and L.

3.1.2. Are there contours hosted by one TBU?

As shown in Table 3 above, monomoraic CV syllables can only bear level tones (H or L). When a tone contour falls on a light syllable, either the vowel is phonetically lengthened to accommodate the contour (Contour-Tone Mora-Addition, §6.2.1) or the contour is simplified through deletion of its final toneme (Final-CV R-to-H Reduction, §6.1.7).

3.2. Inventory of tonemes

3.2.1. Level tonemes

Jamsay has two level tonemes, L and H.

The tonematicity of L is proved by the following criteria:

- The Floating Criterion: L can float (see §3.3 and §7.1.1.2 below);

- The Tonal Morpheme Criterion: there are grammatical tonal morphemes L (see §7, especially §7.1.1);
- The Activity Criterion: L is able to trigger tonal processes (see §6.1, especially §6.1.1, and §7.1.1).

Arguments for the tonemic character of H are the following:

- The Tonal Morpheme Criterion: there are grammatical tonal morphemes H (see §7);
- The Activity Criterion: H is able to trigger tonal processes (see §6.1, especially §6.1.1).

The applicability of the tonal morpheme criterion can be disputed, because either the L or the H grammatical tones could in principle be analyzed as subtractive tonal morphemes. (In fact, tonal morphemes L likely have their origins in the semantization of what originally was a drop of lexical tones in words lacking prosodic prominence (Heath 2020; Heath 2022)). This wouldn't work, however, for the Unaffixed Imperfective (§7.1.1.2), whose exponent is a floating L tone.

When the Unaffixed Imperfective or the other additive L tonal morpheme, the Tonal Locative (§7.1.1.1), applies to a stem ending in a CV syllable bearing a H tone, a HL contour is formed on this final syllable and the vowel undergoes lengthening (§6.2.1 Contour-Tone Mora-Addition) to accommodate it. One wouldn't expect any extra mora to appear if the H tone were inactive (Ø).

Other tonal rules summarized in §6.1 can in principle be restated in terms of a privative system (either H vs. Ø or L vs. Ø), but that would result in many cumbersome and counter-intuitive formulations (e.g., the Toneme Association Rules would have to distinguish between stems that take a toneme on the final mora vs. on all morae but the final; the toneme on the nucleus of the word-final closed syllable would spread to some consonantal codas, but not to others, etc.).

3.2.2. The question of contour tonemes

Jamsay has several tonal melodies that can be reasonably suspected to be tonemes:

- lexical LH melody on verbs;
- lexical LH, HL and LHL melodies on nouns;
- replacive tonal morphemes HL (§§7.1.3.4, 7.1.4.8–7.1.4.10, 7.1.5.2).

However, there appears no reason to postulate contour tonemes. Both levels (L and H) that make up the aforementioned melodies are available as tonemes in their own right. Furthermore, none of these melodies can appear on a single TBU: each level tonal component strictly requires a separate mora. Thus, neither the Non-Compositionality Criterion nor the Extensibility/Single TBU Criterion call for recognition of any contour tonemes in Jamsay.

3.2.3. The question of lexically specified intonation patterns

In a typologically common manner, Jamsay uses clause-final pitch modulations, final segment prolongation and combinations thereof to structure discourse. However, in some cases such intonational devices appear to be part of lexical specification of particular lexemes and morphemes, rather than discourse-driven. Following (Heath 2008), I place these phenomena in the domain of intonation and do not count them as tonemes. However, they clearly straddle the traditional delimitation between lexical tone and intonation (see discussion in (Heath & Sherwood forthc.)), so a brief survey is included herein for completeness sake.

3.2.3.1. Lexically specified prolongation

A number of particles and expressive adverbs (mostly H-toned) are pronounced with exaggerated prolongation (⇒) of the final segment (vowel or sonorant) (Heath 2008: 135–136).

- | | | | |
|-----|--------------------------|---------------------------|-------------------|
| (2) | <i>dém</i> ⇒ | ‘directly, straight’ | |
| | <i>pó</i> ⇒ | ‘directly, straight’ | |
| | <i>sá</i> ⇒ <i>m</i> | ‘to death’ | |
| | <i>àbádá</i> ⇒ | ‘eternally’ | |
| | <i>té</i> ⇒ | ‘precisely, specifically’ | |
| | <i>fú:</i> ⇒, <i>fú:</i> | ‘all, completely’ | (Heath 2008: 136) |

In the case of *sá* ⇒ *m* ‘to death’, it is the penultimate, rather than the final segment which is protracted (contrast it to *dém* ⇒ ‘directly, straight’). With *fú*: ‘all, completely’, the prolongation is optional.

Special prosodic properties are typical of ideophones. Lexical items with final exaggerated prolongation in Jamsay can be viewed as a subclass of ideophones ((Heath 2019), although the author’s preferred term is “expressive adverbials”). The syntactic behaviour of these items also sets them apart (Ibid.).

3.2.3.2. The dying quail word-final intonation

More of a problem is presented by the so-called “dying quail intonation” (Heath 2008: 136–139), because it directly affects pitch and because all its uses can be argued to be tied to specific morphemes. Phonetically, it is characterized by exaggerated prolongation of the final segment (vowel or sonorant), accompanied by a protracted, slow drop in pitch that lasts up to one second.

The dying quail intonation is used:

- on the word *ó*·, which is the standard reply to a called-out greeting (the lexical tone is tentative, since the word doesn’t appear without this intonation);
- at the end of each conjunct in asyndetic NP coordination:

- (3) *ǎ-n*· *ñě-n*· *yěy-yà-bà*
 man-SG woman-SG come-PFV-3PL
 ‘A man and a woman came.’ (Heath 2008: 272)

The dying quail intonation is most conspicuous when the conjuncts are short, becoming almost inaudible on heavy NPs overladen with relative clauses and other material. When the conjoined NP as a whole serves as a head of a relative clause, there arises a conflict between the dying quail intonation and the syntactically motivated L toneme. It is most commonly resolved by retaining the intonational effect on the first conjunct but tone-dropping the second, as in the last option in (4):

- (4) *ǎ-n*· *ñě-n*· *yérè-m* *kùⁿ*
 or: *ǎ-n*· *ñè-n*· *yérè-m* *kùⁿ*
 or: *ǎ-n*· *ñè-n* *yérè-m* *kùⁿ*
 man-SG woman-SG come-PTCP.PL DEF
 ‘the man and the woman who came.’ (Heath 2008: 272)

- on the final syllable of a word immediately preceding the universal quantifier *fú*: (5a), including its clausal-scope uses as a conditional conjunction (5b):

- (5) a. *mì* *yésá*· *bè*· *fú*·
 1SG.P sister.HL PL all
 ‘all (of) my sisters’ (Heath 2008: 255)
- b. *dògùrù* *kó* *ù* *láyá-tì-Ø*· *fú*·
 time.L NHUM.O 2SG.L hit-PFV-PTCP.NHUM all
 ‘when you are finally done with beating it (=hide)’ (Heath 2008: 139)

This intonational effect is found on words of different parts of speech, but generally not on pronouns, which instead receive a L toneme, cf. *ìjú*·: *fú*: ‘all the dogs’ vs. *émè fú*: ‘all of us’ (independent form *émé*). Rarely, the dying quail intonation is observed on pronouns as well.

Another universal quantifier *cêw* ‘all’, which has a very similar, if not identical, range of functions (including use in conditional clauses), does not impose any special intonational effect on the preceding word.

3.3. Floating tones

A floating L toneme is one of the exponents of the Imperfective (Heath 2008: 343, 358–361). If there is a toneless person-number suffix, the floating L docks to its mora. If there is none, it docks leftward to the stem, forming a (L)HL contour on the stem-final syllable. See §7.1.1.1 for more details.

Some (relatively marginal) phenomena can be explained by positing a floating H-tone, but alternative accounts appear preferable (Heath 2008: 122).

3.4. Downdrift and downstep

There is no downstep.

3.5. Upstep

There is no upstep.

3.6. Other suprasegmental features of tonemes, apart from pitch. Interaction of tonemes and phonations. Registers

Tonemes in Jamsay are solely characterized by pitch (unless ∴ is counted as one, which is not the solution adopted here). There are no discernible registers in Jamsay.

4. Tonotactics: tonal span, tonal phrase

4.1. Tonal span boundaries

4.1.1. Tonal span size

Tonal span size varies from a single mora to a sequence of several words (for some replacive grammatical tonemes; see, e.g. §7.1.4.1 for L toneme on head NP in a relative clause, or §7.1.5.1 for L toneme on medial chained verbs). Consider the following example:

- (6) *nîŋ* *èné* *wó* *táː* *wǎː* *tí* *yaĩ* *wàŋ*
 now LOG 3SG.O shoot kill.L LINK.L go.IPFV say
 ‘He said: “Now I will shoot and kill you and (then) go.”’ (Heath 2008: 521)

The final element in the verb chain, *yaĩ* ‘go.IPFV’, bears three tonemes: lexical L and H of the verb stem and L of the Imperfective. The vowel is lengthened to accommodate the latter (per Contour-Tone Mora-Addition, §6.2.1), which then spreads to the following toneless reportative marker (per Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading, §6.1.1): [L *yaĩ*][H *á*][L *à* *wàŋ*]. The first two tonemes thus each occupy one mora. On the other hand, the two medial elements in the same chain, *wǎː* ‘kill’ and the linker *tí*, both undergo tone-dropping as medial chained verbs (§7.1.5.1) and receive a L toneme together: [L *wǎː, ð tí*].

Theoretically, there appears to be no upper limit on the size of the tonal span. In practice, tonal spans covering more than two words are extremely rare.

4.1.2. Establishment of tonal span boundaries

The following tonal rules modify tonal span boundaries:

- Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading (§6.1.1): extends a tonal span rightwards by including subsequent inherently toneless morphemes into it;
- Contour-Tone Stretching (§6.1.3): shifts a monomoraic L tonal span one mora to the right and extends the preceding H tonal span one mora to the right;
- Clitic-Induced Tone Resyllabification (§6.1.4): deletes two monomoraic tonal spans on the *-îː* clitic, then extends the preceding L tonal span rightwards to include both affected morae (although alternative accounts are possible);
- Rightward H-Spreading (§6.1.5): deletes a monomoraic L tonal span (or merges it with that of the clitic), then extends the preceding H span rightwards onto the affected mora.

Tonal span boundaries are also affected by grammatical tones. Most tonal morphemes in Jamsay are replacive: they delete one or more lexical tonemes and impose one (less often, two) grammatical toneme(s) on the same string of TBUs. This often results in redistribution of tonal span boundaries. The two additive grammatical tones, the Tonal Locative (§7.1.1.1) and the Unaffixed Imperfective (§7.1.1.2), may both move the right boundary of the tonal span of a preceding plurimoraic H toneme one mora to the left.

4.1.3. Tonal spans and prosodic units

Tonal span boundaries do not correlate with other kinds of boundaries.

4.2. Combinations of tonemes. Tonal melodies.

Lexical tonal melodies are applied to stems rather than fully inflected words. Possible lexical melodies are H and LH for verbs, H, HL, LH and LHL for other major parts of speech⁵. Only function words and (morphologically defective) underived stative verbs can be inherently L (they also violate the constraint for lexical stems to be at least bimoraic).

Lexical melodies are associated from right to left, with toneme transitions generally occurring closer to the end of the stem. The final toneme in bi- and tritonemic melodies docks to the stem-final mora, except when a LH melody is associated with a nonmonosyllabic CV:-final stem (all such stems are nominal), in which case the final H spans over the entire bimoraic syllable, cf. *bàlpó*: (**bàlpó*.) in (8c). In the LHL melody, after the final L is associated, the first two tonemes are spread over remaining TBUs in such a way as to be separated by a syllable boundary, if possible⁶, as in *jèḡérḡ* in (8e).

Tonal association happens after verbal derivation (e.g. causative formation), cf. the tonal makeup of *bùró*- ‘be revived’ vs. *bùró-gó*- ‘resuscitate’:

- | | | | |
|-----|---------------------|---------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| (7) | ‘be revived’ | ‘resuscitate’ | |
| a. | <i>buro</i> -, {LH} | <i>buro</i> -, CAUS, {LH} | lexical input |
| b. | — | <i>buro-go</i> -, {LH} | derivation |
| c. | <i>bùró</i> - | <i>bùró-gó</i> - | tonal association (Heath 2008: 109) |

Some examples, with toneme associations in graphic form:

- | | | | | | | |
|-----|----|-----------------------|-----------------------------|-------------------------|-------------------------------------|--|
| (8) | a. | {H} on verbal stems: | | | | |
| | | <i>tí</i> :- ‘send’ | <i>úgó</i> - ‘extinguish’ | <i>káḡárḡ</i> - ‘shine’ | <i>káḡárḡ-wḡ</i> - ‘cause to shine’ | |
| | | ti,i | u.go | ka.ḡa.rḡa | ka.ḡa.rḡa.wḡa | |
| | | σ | σ σ | σ σ σ | σ σ σ σ | |
| | | ∧ | ∥ ∥ | ∥ ∥ ∥ | ∥ ∥ ∥ ∥ | |
| | | μ μ | μ μ | μ μ μ | μ μ μ μ | |
| | | ∨ | ∨ | ∨ | ∨ | |
| | | H | H | H | H | |
| | b. | {LH} on verbal stems: | | | | |
| | | <i>wḡ</i> :- ‘kill’ | <i>ùgó</i> - ‘bake in oven’ | <i>ḡḡlḡrḡ</i> - ‘shine’ | <i>ḡḡlḡrḡ-wḡ</i> - ‘cause to snore’ | |
| | | wḡ,ḡ | u.go | ḡḡ.lḡ.rḡ | ḡḡ.lḡ.rḡ.wḡ | |
| | | σ | σ σ | σ σ σ | σ σ σ σ | |
| | | ∧ | ∥ ∥ | ∥ ∥ ∥ | ∥ ∥ ∥ ∥ | |
| | | μ μ | μ μ | μ μ μ | μ μ μ μ | |
| | | ∨ | ∨ | ∨ | ∨ | |
| | | L H | L H | L H | L H | |

⁵ Heath (2008: 89, 99) cites a unique HLH noun (**jí:lùm* ‘leech’), but it was later found to be just HL: *jí:lùm* (Jeffrey Heath, p.c.). The LHL melody only characterizes a handful of noun stems. Further, there are no H-toned numeral stems, but this can be a chance effect, since numerals are a small closed class.

⁶ This last qualification is my addition, the rule is presented as categorical in (Heath 2008: 101). However, as acknowledged in (Heath 2008: 87), “[a] bimoraic first syllable makes RL also possible”. Several examples are provided (see *ḡ:rḡḡ* in (8e)), but they are not counted in the tabulations on which the analysis is based for unclear reasons. I have also (in addition to rewriting the association rules in tonemic terms and stating them in plain prose as compared to Heath’s more formulaic presentation) simplified the conditions on association of the final toneme: the original model made provisions for stem types that are not attested in the language.

- c. {LH} on nominal stems:
- | | | |
|---|---|---|
| <i>ñě-n</i> ‘woman’ | <i>pìnām</i> ‘powder’ | <i>bàlpó:</i> ‘calabash drum’ |
| ñɛ,n | pi.na,m | ba,l.pɔ,ɔ |
| |
- d. {HL} on nominal stems:
- | | | | |
|---|---|--|---|
| <i>dô:</i> ‘Striga herb’ | <i>pé:rè</i> ‘small bowl’ | <i>pí:lòm</i> ‘bladder’ | <i>céllâl</i> ‘health’ |
| do,o | pɛ,e.rɛ | pi,i.lo,m | cɛ,l.la,l |
| |
- e. {LHL} on nominal stems:
- | | |
|--|--|
| <i>ǎ:rⁿò</i> ‘waterskin’ | <i>jèŋjérⁿè</i> ‘small bowl’ |
| ɔ,ɔ.r ⁿ ɔ | jɛ.ŋɛ.r ⁿ ɛ |
| |

Final bimoraic syllables in non-verbal stems have different association properties, depending on whether their weight is due to a consonantal coda or a long vowel, as shown by different tonal makeup of *pìnām* vs. *bàlpó:* in (8c). In (8d), *céllâl* with its final contour shows the regular pattern for consonant-final {HL} nouns, while *pí:lòm* is exceptional.

4.3. Extratonal syllables

In Jamsay, there are no extratonal syllables. A segmental chain can be subdivided into tonal spans without any remainder.

4.4. Tonal phrases

There are no tonal phrases in Jamsay (but see §7.1.4.1 for phrase-level tonal morphemes).

5. Stress and tone; culminativity; prominence; obligatoriness

5.1. Culminativity

Jamsay is not culminative, as it is possible to have more than one toneme per word.

5.2. Stress

Jamsay has no stress.

5.3. Positional prominence

There is no positional prominence in Jamsay, but see §2.2.2 above on the embryonic metrical structure.

5.4. Obligatoriness of tone

Jamsay is characterized by the obligatoriness of tone.

6. Tonal rules

6.1. Tonal rules

Jamsay doesn't manifest any "tonal sandhi" across word boundaries. With the possible exception of Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading (§6.1.1), which may involve spreading of a toneme onto an inherently toneless function word, the rules covered in this section apply locally, at affix or clitic boundaries within a phonological word. They generally have rather specific triggering conditions, with many restricted to particular parts of speech or even particular morphemes.

6.1.1. Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading

A few suffixes and clause-final function words lack intrinsic tone. They are integrated into the tonal span of the toneme associated with the preceding mora (Heath 2008: 118–121). Cf. the following examples:

- (9) a. *jém* 'black'
 SG *jém-ín* PL *jém-úm*
- b. *yà:-* 'go.PFV'
 2PL *yà:-bè* 3PL *yà:-bà*
 yà:-gó- 'go-IPFV.NEG'
 2PL *yà:-gó-bé* 3PL *yà:-gó-bá* (Heath 2008: 118)
- (10) a. *à-kóró* *jà:ⁿ-m* *gá:-jè-bà* *dèy*
 well dig-HORT say-RECPERF-3PL if
 'If they say: "Let's dig a well",...' (Heath 2008: 599)
- b. *kó* *dàyà-lí:-Ø* *déy*
 that leave-PFV.NEG-1PL if
 'If we don't abandon that,..' (Ibid.: 463)
- (11) a. *ñǎ:* *ñè:-jè-Ø* *mà* *wà*
 meal eat-RECPERF-3SG Q QUOT
 'It was asked, did s/he not eat?'
- b. *ñǎ:* *ñè:-lí-Ø* *má* *wá*
 meal eat-PERF.NEG-3SG Q QUOT
 'It was asked, has s/he eaten?' (Ibid.: 119)

This rule doesn't affect the TDI, as it doesn't change either the number of tonemes or the number of syllables/morae:

- (12) *kún-tù-bà* 'put-PERF-3PL.S'
 kú,n-tù-ba → *kú,n-tù-bà*
 H L H L

Toneless monoconsonantal suffixes behave somewhat differently when following a (C)V̂:-final stem; this is covered by Contour-Tone Stretching (§6.1.3).

6.1.2. Pronominal-Suffix Tone-Raising

In the Unsuffix Perfective (§7.1.4.6), a pronominal suffix following a L-final stem can spontaneously surface with a H tone instead of being included into the tonal span of the preceding L (from Atonal Morpheme Tone-Spreading) if followed by some other material within the clause (a clitic or a clause-final particle) (Heath 2008: 121–122). This concerns both syllabic suffixes discussed in the previous subsection (13a) and monomoraic consonantal suffixes (13b):

- (13) a. *kó* *bíré* *é:* *mèyⁿ* *kò-rú* *yòwò-bá=ŷ*
 NHUM.P work see and NHUM-with accept.PFV.L-3PL.H=it.is

is limited to the coda consonant, which is about to lose its moraicity due to resyllabification. The clitic surfaces L-toned.

The rule as formulated above conflates two different rules from the source grammar: Final-Tone Resyllabification (Heath 2008: 126–128) and Clitic <LHL> Reduction (Ibid.: 133–134).

The former rule governs re-linking of the resyllabified consonant’s tone to the right. It has a much broader formulation in the original, intended to cover addition of any V-initial suffix or clitic to a C-final stem or word, like, e.g., the SG marker on adjectives:

- (16) *déŋ* [dé.ŋ] ‘firm’ *déŋ-in* [dé.ŋ-í.ŋ] ‘firm-SG’
ém [è.m] ‘confined’ *ém-in* [è.m-í.ŋ] ‘confined-SG’
tôm [tó.m] ‘cold/slow’ *tôm-in* [tó.m-ì.ŋ] ‘cold/slow-SG’
bá:yⁿ [bá.á.ÿ] ‘newborn’ *bá:yⁿ-in* [bá.á.ÿ-ì.ŋ] ‘newborn-SG’ (Heath 2008: 127)

However, no special rule is required for cases like (16). The observed tonal pattern is straightforwardly accounted for by Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading (provided it applies before resyllabification) and the fact that onset consonants can not bear tones. On the other hand, the tonal behavior of the Focus clitic is clearly idiosyncratic, as acknowledged in (Heath 2008: 80); the general rule as stated in (Ibid.: 128) ends up making wrong predictions for cases like (15b).

Clitic <LHL> Reduction is always fed by Final-Tone Resyllabification. It takes as its input the LHL contour presumably created on the bimoraic clitic by re-linking the L tone of the preceding consonant and simplifies it to just L. A conceivable alternative would be to resolve the conflict by applying Contour-Tone Mora-Addition, lengthening the clitic vowel to trimoraic (*ú:n=i:), but this never happens.

For the purposes of the present analytical report, I chose to substitute these two rules with a single one. Clitic <LHL> Reduction always works in conjunction with the Final-Tone Resyllabification, while those cases when the latter purportedly applies without the subsequent Clitic <LHL> Reduction are best dealt with by other rules.

Note that application of Clitic-Induced Tone-Resyllabification is conditioned not only with inherently C-final stems or words (15d, 17a), but also after a specific case of VV Contraction (§6.2.5), with a L toneme docked to the stem-final syllable (17b).

- (17) a. *ém* ‘milk’ *ém=i:* ‘it is milk’
b. *bé:rù* ‘errand’ *bé:r=i:* ‘it is an errand’ (Heath 2008: 133)

When the Focus clitic attaches to a word ending in a short *-u*, as in (17b), the latter is deleted and the clitic appears in its post-consonantal allomorph. Heath (2008: 130) posits a dedicated rule (Tautosyllabic Stranded-Tone Re-Linking) to account for the subsequent tonal shift, but there is actually no need for it, since this case is already covered by Clitic-Induced Tone-Resyllabification. The presumed derivations for (17a, b) are as follows:

- | | | | |
|------|--------------|-------------------|--------------------------------|
| (18) | ‘it is milk’ | ‘it is an errand’ | comment |
| | /é.m/ + /=y/ | /bé.é.rù/ + /=y/ | |
| | /é.m.=í,ì/ | /bé.é.rù.=í,ì/ | allomorphy and cliticization |
| | " | /bé.é.ɾ.=í,ì/ | VV-contraction, tone-delinking |
| | /é.m=í,ì/ | /bé.é.ɾ=í,ì/ | resyllabification |
| | /é.m=´í,ì/ | /bé.é.r=´í,ì/ | Final-Tone Resyllabification |
| | [é.m=í,ì] | [bé.é.r=í,ì] | Clitic <LHL> Reduction |
- (Heath 2008: 134)

Clitic-Induced Tone-Resyllabification uncovers phonological distinction between unsuffixed perfective and imperfective participles which are homophonous when word-final. Thus, *á:-* ‘catch’ forms plural participles *á:-m̃* in the Imperfective and *á:-m* in the Perfective; despite the difference in transcription, both are phonetically realised as [áám̃] (cf. (14a) above). The exponent of the Imperfective is a floating toneme L which docks to the mora of the nasal suffix, while perfective is marked by a replacive HL contour, the L toneme of which associates with the final mora of the

word, e.g., again that of the suffix. With the addition of the clitic, however, the two participles look as $\acute{a}:-m=\grave{i}$: and $\hat{a}:-m=\grave{i}$: respectively. The derivations are as follows:

- (19) a. Imperfective
 $/\acute{a}:-L-m.=\hat{i}:/$ underlying
 $/\acute{a}:-\grave{m}.=\hat{i}:/$ floating L docks on the suffixal mora
 $/\acute{a}:-\grave{m}=\hat{i}:/$ clitic induces resyllabification
 $/\acute{a}:-m=\hat{i}:/$ Final-Tone Resyllabification
 $/\acute{a}:-m=\grave{i}:/$ Clitic <LHL> Reduction
- b. Perfective
 $/\hat{a}:-m.=\hat{i}:/$ underlying (after the grammatical toneme is applied)
 $/\hat{a}:-m=\hat{i}:/$ clitic induces resyllabification
" " Contour-Tone Stretching (§6.1.3) fails to apply
- (Heath 2008: 128)

(19b) shows that clitic-induced resyllabification happens before (and bleeds) Contour-Tone Stretching, otherwise one would get $/\hat{a}:-m=\hat{i}:/ \rightarrow \#/\hat{a}:-\grave{m}=\hat{i}:/$, and thence the derivation would proceed the same as for the Imperfective.

The effect of Clitic-Induced Tone-Resyllabification on the TDI is not a straightforward question. One way to explain the contour tone reduction is to assume that the stranded stem-final L toneme, having no vacant mora to dock to, deletes the initial H toneme of the clitic to take its place. Under this logic, the resulting L tone on the clitic would be bi-tonemic: the tone of its first mora belongs to the stem-final L toneme, while the tone of the second constitutes the intrinsic L toneme of the clitic. An alternative is to consider both morae of the clitic to fall into the span of a single L toneme, and this is the solution adopted here for simplicity's sake. Thus, Clitic-Induced Tone-Resyllabification is taken to always delete two tonemes, reducing the TDI. The impact is somewhat less on the moraic TDI, as resyllabification also eliminates one mora, while retaining the number of syllables.

6.1.5. Rightward H-Spreading

When a quasi-verb $=k\grave{o}$ 'be (nonhuman)' or $=w\grave{o}$ 'be (human)' is cliticized to an adjective bearing a lexical HL toneme combination, the H toneme spreads to the final mora of the adjective, displacing the L-toneme, which merges with that of the quasi-verb.

Cf. $\acute{o}g\grave{u}$ 'hot, fast' : $\acute{o}g\acute{u}=k\grave{o}$ 'it is hot, fast' : $\acute{o}g\acute{u}=w\grave{o}$'s/he is hot, fast'; $t\acute{o}m$ 'slow' : $t\acute{o}m=k\grave{o}$ 'it is slow'; $j\acute{e}:r\acute{u}$ 'hot, fast' : $j\acute{e}:r\acute{u}=k\grave{o}$ 'it is hot, fast', etc. (Heath 2008: 129).

This rule is restricted to adjectives and doesn't apply to adverbials, although they can be used predicatively with the same quasi-verbs in a very similar manner, cf. $j\acute{o}b\grave{u}$ 'soaking wet' : $j\acute{o}b\grave{u}=k\grave{o}$ 'it is soaking wet'.

Rightward H-Spreading conflates two tonemes into one, thus decreasing the TDI.

6.1.6. Exosyllabic Stranded-Tone Re-Linking

One more case of tone stranding and subsequent re-linking occurs when a monomoraic CV syllable loses its vowel due to Post-Sonorant Syncope (§6.2.2) or one of the apocope rules (§6.2.3–6.2.4). In this scenario, delinked H and L tones show somewhat different behavior.

A H tone always re-links to the left, either merging with the final H of the preceding syllable (20a) or creating a LH contour if said syllable is L-toned (20b)⁷. A L tone re-links to the left only if followed by a H tone (20c); when followed by another L tone, it just disappears (20d).

- (20) a. $p\acute{e}r\acute{e}$ - 'clap' $p\acute{e}t-t\grave{i}$ - 'clap-PFV'
b. $d\grave{u}r\acute{o}$ - 'groan' $d\ddot{u}t-t\grave{i}$ - 'groan-PFV' (Heath 2008: 58)
 $d\grave{i}\eta-\acute{u}$ 'sit.down.L-NMR' $d\grave{i}\eta$
 $b\grave{e}-r\acute{u}$ '3PL-DAT' $b\check{e}-r\acute{g}\acute{a}-\grave{w}$ '3PL-DAT say.IPFV-2SG' (Heath 2008: 130)

⁷ In (20a) and the first example of (20b), the tone is stranded as a result of Post-Sonorant Syncope; in the second example of (20b), it's Suffixal *u*-Apocope, and further examples in (20b–d) involve Inter-Word *u*-Apocope.

6.2.2. Post-Sonorant Syncope

A short vowel is deleted if:

- it is in the metrically weak σ_2 position in a (C)VCV verbal stem; and
- it is preceded by a (coronal) rhotic $\{r^n\}$; and
- it is followed by a suffix-initial coronal $\{t d n s l r\}$ or y , or by Linker $tí$; and
- the vowel of the first syllable in the (C)VCV stem is also short. (Heath 2008: 56–60)

The tone of the syncopated vowel is subject to Exosyllabic Stranded-Tone Re-Linking (§6.1.6), particularly ex. (20a,b)). The now adjacent consonants are affected by various assimilatory processes.

- (22) *sír-é-* ‘cook’ + *-tì* PFV → *sít-tì-*
bèr-é- ‘find’ + *-sà* RES → *běs-sà-*
yèr-é- ‘come’ + *-lí* PFV.NEG → *yěl-lí*
gàr-á- ‘pass’ + *-yà* PFV → *gǎy-yà-*
bòr-ǎ- ‘summon’ + *-tì* PFV → *bǒn-tì-*
mòr-ǎ- ‘assemble’ + *-yà* PFV → *mǒyⁿ-yà-* (Heath 2008: 57–59)

This rule only applies to verbs (and their deverbal nouns). The consonant in the rightward context usually belongs to an aspect-polarity suffix, as in (22), but can also be part of a derivational suffix (Reversive in (23b)) or the Linker $tí$ (23c):

- (23) a. *páy-á-* ‘tie’ + *-rV* REV → *páyá-rá-* ‘untie’
 b. *pír-é-* ‘get stuck’ + *-rV* REV → *píl-lé-* ‘get unstuck’
kór-ǎ- ‘hang up, hook’ + *-rV* REV → *kól-lǎ-* ‘uhook’
màr-á- ‘be lost’ + *-rV* REV → *màl-lá-* ‘be recovered’ (Heath 2008: 60)
 c. *kár-á-* ‘do, make’ → *kán tí mèy*† ‘make... (and...)’

There is a number of irregularities and idiosyncrasies in the application of this rule. In particular, there is a handful of cases when Post-Sonorant Syncope exceptionally affects a stem-final vowel after a nasal, rather than coronal (in violation of condition (b)) and/or after the σ_1 with a long vowel (in violation of condition (d)):

- (24) *kún-ó-* ‘bring’ + *-tì* PFV → *kún-tì-*
jè:r-é- ‘bring’ + *-tì* PFV → *jět-tì-*
mǎ:-nǎ- ‘bring together’ + *-tì* PFV → *mǎ:n-tì- / mǎ:-nǎ-tì-*

Post-Sonorant Syncope is one of the rules that point to the embryonic metrical structure (§2.2.2). Condition (d) sets it apart from *g*-Spirantization, which is insensitive to vowel length in σ_1 . However, this restriction can be naturally explained by the motivation to avoid an undesirable superheavy syllable (CV:C) and thus doesn’t constitute an argument against monophonematically of long vowels.

This rule increases the (syllabic) TDI, because it deletes a syllable (but not a mora) and doesn’t affect the tonemes (that are then taken care of by Exosyllabic Stranded-Tone Re-Linking).

6.2.3. Suffixal *u*-Apocope

In disyllabic verbal nouns, the suffixal *-u* is optionally deleted after an unclustered nasal (other than \tilde{n}) or a semivowel.

- (25) *bùm-ó-* ‘drag’ : *bùm-ú, bŭm*
ná:ná- ‘put up on’ : *nà:n-ú, nǎ:n*
mǎŋ-ǎ- ‘massage’ : *mǎŋ-ú, mǎŋ*
éw-é- ‘buy’ : *èw-ú, ěw*
ná:-wⁿá- ‘greet in the morning’ : *nà:-wⁿ-ú, nǎ:-wⁿ*
ǎy-ǎ- ‘rot’ : *ǎy-ú, ǎy*
gùyⁿ-ó- ‘rob’ : *gùyⁿ-ú, gŭyⁿ* (Heath 2008: 62)

This is another rule targeting the metrically weak position in σ_2 . As can be seen from the examples above, it applies irrespective of the vowel length in σ_1 . The H tone of the apocopated vowel is subject to Exosyllabic Stranded-Tone Re-Linking (§6.1.6), forming a LH contour on the surviving syllable (the nominalizing suffix carries a H toneme and imposes a L replacive grammatical toneme on the preceding stem, cf. §7.1.2.3).

Application of this optional rule increases the (syllabic) TDI, because it deletes a syllable (but not a mora) and doesn't affect the tonemes (that are preserved by Stranded-Tone Re-Linking).

6.2.4. Inter-Word *u*-Apocope

Final *-u* in a disyllabic compound initial, in a disyllabic word immediately preceding a verb or a 'be' quasi-verb, or in a nonfinal disyllabic word in a phrase is optionally deleted, primarily between velar stops or after *r*, especially before a coronal (Heath 2008: 68).

This rule probably amalgamates several distinct, though outwardly similar processes, all targeting *-u* in the metrically weak position in various environments. The formulation above glosses over many finer details and idiosyncrasies (Heath 2008: 63–68).

(26)	<i>bèrú</i> 'goat' + <i>ná:</i> 'body'	:	<i>bèn-ná:</i> 'goat' (compound)
	<i>dùgú</i> 'fat' + <i>kùⁿ</i> DEF	:	<i>dùg kùⁿ</i> 'the fat' (N + determiner)
	<i>dùgú</i> 'fat' + <i>kâ.ⁿ</i> 'each, any'	:	<i>dùg kâ.ⁿ</i> 'each fat' (N + quantifier)
	<i>bèrú</i> 'goat' + <i>cètè</i> 'runty'	:	<i>bèr cètè</i> 'runty goat' (N + A)
	<i>bè-rú</i> 3PL-DAT + <i>té:ré-</i> 'show'	:	<i>běr té:ré-</i> 'show them' (Prn + V)
	<i>yìrú</i> 'garment' + <i>té:ré-</i> 'show'	:	<i>yìr té:ré-</i> 'show garments' (N + V)
	<i>ógù</i> 'fast' + <i>=kò</i> 'be (nonhuman)	:	<i>óg=kò</i> 'it's fast' (A + QuasiV)
	<i>bórù</i> '(smb's) uncle' + <i>nè</i> 'now'	:	<i>mí bón nè</i> 'my uncle now' (N + particle)
	<i>bórù</i> '(smb's) uncle' + <i>tírwè-n</i> 'grandchild'	:	
	:	:	<i>...bór tírwè-n</i> '(smb's) uncle's grandchild' (PssrN + PssmN)

(Heath 2008: 66–67)

Again, if the tone of the apocopated vowel is the only one of its toneme, the latter can be preserved via Exosyllabic Stranded-Tone Re-Linking. (Cf. *dùg kùⁿ* in (26), which preserves both lexical tonemes of *dùgú*; the L tone on the same segmental form in *dùg kâ.ⁿ* is because the universal quantifier places L tonal morpheme on the preceding noun, c.f. §7.1.4.1).

Similar to the two preceding vowel deletion rules, application of Inter-Word *u*-Apocope eliminates one syllable, but doesn't affect the number of either morae or tonemes. It thus increases the syllabic (but not the moraic) TDI.

6.2.5. VV Contraction

There is a number of contexts where a contraction of adjacent vowels occurs:

- (27)
- a. in non-monosyllabic Verbal Nouns with suffix *-ú*;
 - b. in a subset of compounds with final *-i.ⁿ* 'child';
 - c. when C_2 of a C_1VC_2V stem is idiosyncratically deleted (in causatives or aspect-polarity forms of a few verbs);
 - d. when 3PL.S *-ba* has its initial *b* deleted after a negative -CV aspect-polarity suffix;
 - e. when a predicated *u*-final adjective is followed by an "augment" *-í.⁸*;
 - f. when a word attaches the specificational/focus clitic *=í:*;
 - g. when a verb stem is suffixed with *-á:rà* PROG (Heath 2008: 72).

The cases in (27a–g) are governed by different sub-rules that do not easily conflate into a uniform formulation; all but (27c) are probably influenced by morphological factors. Sometimes the first vowel is deleted with compensatory lengthening of the second, sometimes without; sometimes the output vowel combines features from both inputs. The finer details are of little

⁸ This is a suffix that emphasizes permanence, ruling out a transient-quality reading (Heath 2008: 181). It has a different allomorph (vowel lengthening) with adjective stems endings in vowels other than *u*, which is irrelevant for the VV Contraction rule.

concern to us here. As regards the tonal realization (when tones on the two vowels are not identical), there are two possibilities. In the case of the clitic =*i*·, the resulting tone can be taken from either V₁ or V₂, depending on the circumstances; this has already been covered in §6.1.4. In all other relevant contexts, the resulting tone is that of V₂.

VV Contraction is relevant for the TDI calculation. It always deletes a syllable and in most (but not all) cases also deletes a mora (or even two). It may also delete a toneme.

7. Grammatical and lexical tones

7.1. List of grammatical tonal morphemes

Jamsay possesses a vast array of grammatical tonal morphemes, which participate in inflection, derivation and compounding. To some of them it may be difficult to ascribe a signified: their presence is triggered by a specific syntactic configuration rather than by a well-defined grammatical feature. I speak of tonal morphemes in all cases where (i) a segmental morph appears with tones other than its lexical melody; and (b) this tonal change is morphosyntactically or semantically driven rather than due to interaction between tonemes. Still, the line between tonal morphemes and tonal rules is somewhat blurry in Dogon languages.⁹

Another complicated issue concerns tonal spans. Most grammatical tonal morphemes in Jamsay are replacive. Although Heath (2008: 8, 10ff) treats all replacive grammatical tones as stem-wide, many are best viewed as applying to a word or even a constituent, as acknowledged from the start in (Heath & McPherson 2013)¹⁰. A stem-level character is most evident when a grammatically-induced toneme is applied to the stem but not to the suffix, which bears its own toneme. However, many grammatical tonal morphemes are found in forms that only contain a toneless suffix or no suffixes at all. In such cases there is no direct evidence to characterize the tonal morpheme in question as stem- vs. word-level.

This rather large subsection is structured as follows. §7.1.1 introduces the two additive tonal morphemes. §7.1.2 covers replacive tonal morphemes that are undisputably stem-level, e.g., apply to a stem in combination with an independently toned suffix. In §7.1.3 I survey a vast inventory of tone changes involved in compound formation, which may also be viewed as stem-level tonal morphemes. §7.1.4 describes a diverse bunch of grammatical tones that I characterize as “syntactically-conditioned”; these are presumably word- or phrase-based, with the caveat stated at the end of the preceding paragraph. Finally, §7.1.5 is concerned with tonal changes involved in verb chaining and verb repetition: these are phenomena whose status on the continuum between clausal syntax and compounding is somewhat debatable, hence a separate subsection. Within each subsection, grammatical tonal morphemes are listed in the general order from nominal to verbal (with adjectival, etc. in-between) and from L to H to HL, with a few deviations where necessary.

7.1.1. Additive L tonal morphemes

There are only two additive tonal morphemes: the Tonal Locative (limited to a number of nouns) and the Unaffixed Imperfective. In both cases, the exponent is a L toneme which is grafted to the final mora of the word without erasing any lexical tonemes. Heath (2008: 113–117) postulates a dedicated rule of Tone-Grafting to account for this, but it is only relevant for these two tonal morphemes and the details of application are somewhat different between the two cases, so I cover the relevant data here.

7.1.1.1. Tonal Locative

Tonal Locatives can be formed from a closed set of nouns¹¹, all of which have a final H toneme. If the tonal span of this H toneme is more than a mora, the grammatical L toneme of the Tonal Locative occupies the final mora (28a–b); if the tonal span is restricted to the final mora, the

⁹ In fact, Tone Dissimilation in decimal numerals, for which a peculiar tonal morpheme is postulated below in §7.1.3.1, is accounted for via a dedicated rule of tonal morphophonology in (Heath 2008: 117).

¹⁰ Cf. also: “The interesting aspect of the system is that these tonal morphemes can potentially overwrite the tone of multiple words; they are phrasal rather than word-level in their scope.” (McPherson & Heath 2016: 606).

¹¹ Some postpositions are historically Tonal Locatives, cf. (28d).

respective vowel is lengthened according to the Contour-Tone Mora-Addition to accommodate both the lexical H and the grammatical L (28c–e):

(28)	a.	<i>ká:</i>	‘mouth’	<i>kâ:</i>	‘at the mouth’	
	b.	<i>úró</i>	‘house’	<i>úrò</i>	‘in the house’	
	c.	<i>gǎ:</i>	‘granary’	<i>gǎ̃:</i>	‘in the granary’	
	d.	<i>gǔn</i>	‘body’	<i>gǔññ</i>	‘behind’ (postposition)	
	e.	<i>bòrǒ</i>	‘bottom’	<i>bòrǒ:</i>	‘at the bottom’	(Heath 2008: 114)

7.1.1.2. Unsuffixed Imperfective

The exponent of the Unsuffixed Imperfective is a floating L toneme suffixed to verbal stems, which can be of the type CṾ:-, CṾ̃:- or (...)CṾ- (§4.2). Unlike the Tonal Locative, which can never be followed by any other affixes, the Unsuffixed Imperfective is normally followed by either pronominal subject markers or participial suffixes, which are toneless and can be of the shape -Ø, -C or -CV. When the following suffix is overt, the grammatical L toneme docks rightward to its only mora. When it is -Ø (3SG/PTCP.NHUM), the L toneme docks leftward to the stem, resulting in a (L)HL contour on the final vowel, which may undergo Contour-Tone Mora-Addition to accommodate it (29b–c).

(29)	verb	3SG IPFV	1SG IPFV	3PL IPFV	
	a.	<i>tí:-</i> ‘send’	<i>tí:-Ø</i>	<i>tí:-m̃</i>	<i>tí:-bà</i>
	b.	<i>yǎ:-</i> ‘go’	<i>yǎ̃:-Ø</i> [yàáà]	<i>yǎ:-m̃</i> [yàá-m̃]	<i>yǎ:-bà</i>
	c.	<i>jùgǒ-</i> ‘know’	<i>jùgǒ:-Ø</i>	<i>jùgǒ-m̃</i>	<i>jùgǒ-bà</i>

The Unsuffixed Imperfective can in principle be also followed by the clitic =*kò* ‘be (nonhuman)’, in which case its L toneme is merged with that of the clitic (see §6.1.5 for a similar process of Rightward H-Spreading).

Note that in zero-suffixed forms, the tonal span of the stem-final H toneme always overlaps with the final syllable, which sets Unsuffixed Imperfective apart from the Tonal Locative, cf. *úrò* ‘house’ : *úrò* ‘in the house’ vs. *páyá-* ‘tie’ : *páyá:-Ø* / **páyà-Ø* ‘tie.IPFV.3SG’.

Forms like *tí:-bà* in (33a) prove the floating character of the L toneme of the Unsuffixed Imperfective. If it were simply a grammatical tone first grafted on the stem, then spread rightwards to the suffix per Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading, one would expect **tí:-bà*.

7.1.2. Stem-level replacive tonal morphemes

7.1.2.1. Stem-level replacive L tone morpheme on dative personal pronouns

Dative personal pronouns arguably involve a stem-wide L toneme imposed by the suffix. For more details, see §7.1.4.2, where grammatical tones within the pronominal system are discussed.

7.1.2.2. Stem-level replacive L tone morpheme on negated predicates

Negative suffixes generally impose a L toneme on the stem they attach to (note that no stem can be lexically all-L). These include:

- 1) Negative aspect-polarity suffixes: *-gò* IPFV.NEG and *-lí* PFV.NEG (Heath 2008: 368–371).
- | | | | | |
|------|----|-----------------------------|----------------------------------|-------------------|
| (30) | a. | <i>yǎ:-yè-Ø</i> ‘s/he went’ | <i>yà:-lí-Ø</i> ‘s/he didn’t go’ | (Heath 2008: 368) |
| | b. | <i>dèné-m̃</i> ‘I want’ | <i>dèné-gó-m̃</i> ‘I don’t want’ | (Ibid.: 370) |
- 2) The Prohibitive *-ỵ* (Heath 2008: 378–379). Cf. *yèrè-ỵ* ‘don’t you_{SG} come!’ (from *yèré-* ‘come’).
 - 3) Stative negative suffix *-rǒ* : *-rá*, used for negation of a closed set of underived stative verbs (Heath 2008: 401, 417–418. 436). Cf. *wǒ:-rǒ* ‘not be (human)’ (from *wó* ‘be (human)’), *kǒ:-rǒ* ‘not be (non-human)’ (from *kó* ‘be (non-human)’), *sà:-rá* ‘not have’ (from *sá* ‘have’)¹².

¹² In (Heath 2008) the three statives under discussion are given with L tones, as *wò*, *kò* and *sà* respectively. However, a different analysis is sketched in (Heath 2020: 116), under which their lexical tones are H and the fact that they always appear L-toned in main clauses is ascribed to defocalization (§7.1.4.6).

- 4) Stative negative marker =*lá*¹³, used for negation of adjectival predicates (31) and derived stative verbs (32).

- (31) a. *ér=kò*
sweet=be.NHUM
'It is sweet.' (*érù*) (Heath 2008: 432)
- b. *èl=lá*
sweet=NEG
'It is not sweet.' (Ibid.: 433)
- (32) a. *jòwⁿlè ànà pěyⁿ dá:ⁿ-tòyò mèyⁿ...*
Dianwely.L village.L old be.sitting-IPFV and
'Sitting (=dwelling) in Old Dianwelly,...'
- b. *nì.dí:ⁿ dà:ⁿ=lá-bá*
here be.sitting-NEG-3PL
'They are not sitting here' (Ibid.: 424)

The same clitic is also involved in a rare strategy for negation of imperfective verbs. Normally, *-gò-* IPFV.NEG substitutes positive imperfective suffixes, as in (30b). However, *-á:rà-* PROG and *-tòyò-* IPFV may instead be followed directly by =*lá*, in which case no L toneme is imposed¹⁴:

- (33) a. *bìr-á:rà-m* 'I work' *bìr-á:rà=lá-m* 'I don't usually work'
- b. *yá:-tòyò-m* 'I go (often)' *yá:-tòyò=lá-m* 'I don't go (often)' (Ibid.: 371)

In (Heath 2020: 118), a generalization is put forward to the effect that negative verbal suffixes and enclitics in Jamsay always control a tone drop (in our terms, impose a L toneme) on the preceding stem, while positive suffixes and enclitics never do so. Heath (2008: 381–382) also lists the Hortative suffixes *-m* (singular addressee) and *-máyⁿ* (plural addressee) as inducing tone lowering on the preceding stem, which contradicts the second part of the above-cited generalization (the Hortative is listed among relevant verbal categories (Heath 2020: 115), but receives no dedicated discussion in the article). However, subsequent fieldwork has shown that the description in the grammar is not fully correct: only LH verb stems change to all-L, while H stems retain their H tones (Jeffrey Heath, p.c.). The tonal change in Hortative forms can be accounted for in several ways; I refrain from making a final decision as more data is desirable. There are no relevant forms in the sampled text.

7.1.2.3. Stem-level replacive L tone morpheme on nominalized verbs

The above-listed negative suffixes share their property of imposing a L toneme on preceding with the nominalizing suffix *-y* (for monosyllabic stems)/*-ú* (for others). Since the stem-final vowel is deleted, the effect is only audible with H (but not LH) stems. Cf. *tí:-* 'send' : *tù-y*, *yá:-* 'go' : *yà-y*, *bàrá-* 'gather' : *bàr-ú*, *jàngíné-* 'teach' : *jàngùn-ú* (Heath 2008: 151–152).

In addition, there is a set of trimoraic nouns of clearly deverbal origins that have a H toneme spanning the whole word. These may be formed with *-ú*, some other derivational suffix, or be unaffixed (Heath 2008: 153–154). Since the derivation pattern is clearly unproductive, this case is not counted among the grammatical tones of Jamsay.

7.1.2.4. Stem-level replacive H tonal morpheme on verbs

In two cases, verbal suffixes impose a H toneme on the stem they attach to. Obviously, the effect is only audible with LH (but not H) stems.

- 1) In the Imperative (*-Ø* for singular addressee; *-y* for plural addressee), the majority of bomoraic ((C)V:- or (C)VCV-) verbal stems receive a H toneme. Cf. *yèré-* 'come', *yéré*

¹³ This negator is described as a suffix in (Heath 2008), but has been reclassified into a clitic in (Heath 2020). Indeed, at least in some contexts it can appear alternatively either before (as in (32b)–(33)) or after subject agreement suffixes.

¹⁴ See also the discussion of (44) in §7.1.4.1 below.

‘come!_{SG}’, *yéré-y* ‘come!_{PL}’. Stems containing three or more morae, as well as a handful of exceptional bimoraic stems, retain their lexical tonemes in the Imperative.

- 2) A specific type of temporal adverbial clauses employs a form in *-wV̇* (Heath 2008: 559–566). This suffix is segmentally identical to the causative *-wV̇*, but carries the opposite toneme¹⁵. It also appears to have a nominalizing function (as the resulting form is introduced by a locative postposition and has its subject encoded as possessor) and doesn’t convey any semantics of causation. The verbal stem in such a form receives a H toneme:

- (34) a. *kó máyⁿá-wⁿà lè*
 NHUM.P dry.H-NMLZ in
 ‘before it dries’ (*màyⁿá-* ‘dry’) (Heath 2008: 561)
- b. *mì dē: árá mà sá:kù wó jé:rē-wè lè*
 1SG.P.L father.HL rice POSS sack 3SG.P bring.H-NMLZ in
 ‘my father_{TOP}, before he brings a sack of rice’ (*jé:rē-* ‘bring’) (Ibid: 563)

7.1.3. Replacive tonal morphemes in compound formation

Jamsay makes ample use of compounding, especially in its nominal lexicon. In most types of composite words, one or both of the compounded stems receive a special tonal marking.

7.1.3.1. Tone Dissimilation (decimal numerals)

Multiples of 10 are formed as compounds of *péru* ‘10’ and a single-digit numeral, e.g.:

- (35) *pél-lěy* ‘20’
pén-nú:yⁿ ‘50’
pèrù-kúróy ‘60’
pèrù-súyⁿ ‘70’
pèl-lá:rúwà ‘90’

The initial *péru* receives a toneme opposite to the first toneme of the final. This is the only tone dissimilation process attested in Jamsay, unless a dissimilatory account of Pronominal-Suffix Tone-Raising (§6.1.2) is adopted. In (Heath 2008: 117), this process is treated as a special rule of tonal morphophonology, but I cover it here, among other replacive grammatical tones involved in compound formation. Under the dissimilatory account adopted here, the rule deletes one toneme (the tones on ‘ten’ are automatic and non-discriminatory) and so decreases the TDI. (The segmental shape of the initial in ‘20’, ‘50’ and ‘90’ (also in ‘30’ and ‘40’) is due to Post-Sonorant Syncope (§6.2.1) and subsequent assimilation).

7.1.3.2. Stem-level replacive L tonal morphemes in compounds

There are several types of compounds that have either the initial or the final stem bear a L toneme:

- 1) Compounds of the type $\check{X}\bar{N}$ (Heath 2008: 192–193). The final component is the head noun, denoting the referent; it retains its lexical tones. The initial component is a modifier characterizing the referent with respect to location, origins, salient property, etc; it can be of varying syntactic category (though all examples provided in the respective subsection involve nouns) and receives a L toneme. Cf. *tòrò-ñě-m* mountain.L-woman-PL ‘women from villages in the hills’ (*tòrò*); *ěñě-bé:* chicken.L-excrement ‘chicken excrement’ (*ěñě*); *kù:n-nùⁿó* head.L-pain ‘flu with headache’ (*kù:n*).
- 2) Compounds of the type $\check{X}\bar{V}_{MSD}$ (Heath 2008: 193–196). This is a subtype of the previous pattern where the final component is a verbal noun. The initial, which undergoes tone-dropping, can be viewed as an incorporated argument of the verbal noun; it usually has a generic meaning. Many compounds of this type have somewhat idiosyncratic meanings.

¹⁵ Strictly speaking, the causative suffix doesn’t carry any toneme of its own, but since it attaches to the stem before tonal association and since lexical tonal melodies for verbs are all H-final (cf. §6.1.1), its vowel always has a H tone, unless any grammatical tonal morphemes are applied.

- Cf. *bà:ñà-lǝw* bowl.L-carve.MSD ‘carving of wooden bowls’ (*bà:ñá*); *dì:n-nà-ýⁿ* place.L-spend.night-MSD ‘(animal’s) place for spending the night’ (*dí:n*); *gò:rò-tǝwⁿ* kola.L-chew.MSD ‘chewing kola nuts; a price of kola (a small gift of money)’ (*gó:rò*); *cìnè-yǎŋ* shadow.L-look.MSD ‘mirror’ (*cì-ciné*).
- 3) Compounds with the final component *-sà:-rá* ‘the fact of not having X’ (Heath 2008: 196). While quasi-verbs like *sá:-* ‘have’ cannot form verbal nouns, the negative form *-sà:-rá* can be used, without additional suffixation, as a final component in nominal compounds. The initial receives a L toneme, cf. *tǝyⁿǝ-sà:-rá* ‘not having truth, being in the wrong’.
 - 4) Nominalized verb-verb-verb compounds (Heath 2008: 198–199). See below in §7.1.3.3, (2).
 - 5) Agentive compounds of the type $\dot{N}\dot{V}_{PTCP}$ (Heath 2008: 201–203). The initial component is a nominal stem (sometimes a lexicalized noun + adjective combination, or, occasionally, an instrumental PP) and the final component is a verb in participial form. The initial component receives a L toneme, while the final receives a H toneme. Cf. *tàrà-yá:-m* collective.hunt.L-go.H-PTCP.PL ‘those who go on collective hunts’ (*tàrà, yǎ:-*); *àsègè-háybé-m* animal.L-follow.H-PTCP.PL ‘herders; those who follow livestock to pasture’; *nùŋ-nùŋó-n* dance_N.L-dance_V.H-PTCP.SG ‘dancer’; *ì:n-bà:yⁿ-íni-rⁿé-m* [child-newborn].L-[bathe-CAUS].L-PTCP.PL ‘midwives; those who bathe the newborn child’.
 - 6) Compounds of the type $\dot{X}\dot{V}_{PTCP}$ (Heath 2008: 201). This is a very rare pattern, in which the initial component is a verbal or adjectival stem and the final component is a verb in participial form. The initial component receives a L toneme, while the final receives a HL combination (characteristic of Unaffixed Perfective participles, see §7.1.4.10), with the L associated to the final mora. Cf. *yà:-yèrè-m* go.L-come.HL-PTCP.PL ‘the go-and-come women (a caste name)’ (*yǎ:-, yèrè-*).
 - 7) Compounds with the final component *-î:n* ‘child of’ (Heath 2008: 204–206)¹⁶. The human noun ‘child’ (SG *î-n*, PL *úrⁿ-ùm*) corresponds to the non-human *-î:n* ‘child of an/juvenile animal’. The latter can function as a final component in nominal compounds, with the initial component receiving a L toneme. When the initial component ends in a short vowel, VV Contraction sometimes occurs. Cf. *ij-î:n* ‘puppy’ (*ijú* ‘dog’); *nà:m-î:n* ‘cotton grain’ (*nǎ:m* ‘cotton’); *nùmò-î:n* ‘finger, tree branch’ (*nùmó* ‘hand’); *jàràwà-î:n* ‘metal part of hoe (excluding wooden handle)’ (*járáwá* ‘hoe’).
 - 8) Compounds with the final components *-àrⁿá* ‘male’ and *-yǎ:* ‘female’ (Heath 2008: 206–208). The initial component receives a L toneme. Cf. *tìrè-àrⁿá* ‘male ancestor’ vs. *tìrè-yǎ:* ‘female ancestor’ (*tìré* ‘grandparent’ (unpossessed)); *ijù-àrⁿá* ‘male dog’ vs. *ijù-yǎ:* ‘female dog’ (*ijú* ‘dog’); *nàmsègè-àrⁿá* ‘*Cryptocatantops* sp.’ vs. *nàmsègè-yǎ:* ‘*Diabolocatantops* sp.’ (*nàmségè* ‘grasshopper of the subfamily Catantopidae’); *nùmò-àrⁿá* ‘thumb’ (*nùmó* ‘hand’); *àyà-yǎ:* ‘(woman’s) co-wife’ (*áyà* ‘husband’).
 - 9) Compounds with the final component *-ná:* ‘authentic, entire’ (< *nǎ:* ‘mother’) (Heath 2008: 204–206). Cf. *àrⁿàkǝyⁿ-ná:* ‘large boubou’ (*àrⁿàkǝyⁿ* ‘boubou’); *bèrù-ná:* ‘common goat breed’ (*bèrú* ‘goat’); *è:rè-ná:* ‘groundnut’ (*é:rè* ‘peanut spp.’); *ǝyǝ-ná:-n* ‘true Lord (i.e. God)’ (*ǝyǝ-n* ‘chief’).
 - 10) Adjectival compounds of the type $\dot{N}\bar{A}$ (Heath 2008: 221). The initial component is a nominal stem that receives a L toneme and the final component is an adjective that keeps its lexical toneme(s). The tonal makeup is thus the same as in a simple noun + adjective combination (see §7.1.4.1), but the semantics is different. Cf. *ǝyǝ-ǝrú* ‘green’ (*ǝyǝ* ‘grass’, *ǝrú* ‘fresh, soft and moist’).
 - 11) Adjectival compounds of the type $\dot{A}-nà:-\bar{A}$ (Heath 2008: 222). This type involves two instances of the same adjective linked by the medial *-nà:-*. It has an intensifying function. The initial repetition receives a L toneme, while the final keeps its lexical toneme(s), cf. *pèyⁿ-nà:-pèyⁿ* ‘very old’ (*pèyⁿ* ‘old’).

¹⁶ Compounds subsumed under (7)–(9) here can be viewed as subtypes of the more general pattern in (1) above.

- 12) Adjectival compounds with the final component *-lógó* ‘very’ (Heath 2008: 222–223). Another intensifying compounding type, in which the initial adjective likewise receives a L toneme, cf. *gùrù-lógó* ‘very long’ (*gùrú* ‘long, tall’).

7.1.3.3. Stem-level replacive H tonal morphemes in compounds

There are at least two types of compounds in which either the initial or the final stem receives a H toneme:

- 1) Agentive compounds of the type $\dot{N}\dot{V}_{PTCP}$ (Heath 2008: 201–203). These have already been covered as (5) in the previous subsection.
- 2) Nominalized verb-verb compounds of the type $\bar{V}(\dot{V})\dot{V}$ (Heath 2008: 198–199). Two or three verbal stems can be joined together and function as a noun, without any segmental markers of nominalization. The initial stem retains its lexical toneme(s), the medial (if there’s one) receives a L toneme, and the final receives a H toneme. Cf. *jìñé-yàṅà-bé:-bé:* sniff-look.L-excrement-defecate.H ‘sniff-look-and-shit’ (a playful name for Scorpion in a tale; *yàṅà-* ‘look’, *bé:-* ‘defecate’); *sára-báyá* have.diarrhoea-be.cured.H ‘have-diarrhoea-and-be-cured’ (a medical treatment involving a laxative; *báyá-* ‘be cured’). In a context where a noun undergoes tone-dropping (see §7.1.4.1), such deverbal compound receives a L toneme that spans over all its stems.

7.1.3.4. Stem-level replacive HL tonal morphemes in compounds

Several types of compounds have a HL contour on the final component:

- 1) Compounds of the type $\dot{X}\dot{V}_{PTCP}$ (Heath 2008: 201). This rare pattern has already been covered as (6) in §7.1.3.2.
- 2) Compounds of the type $\bar{X}\hat{N}$ (Heath 2008: 197–198). The final component is the logical head, while the initial component specifies its origin or property. Cf. *dómno-ñé-m* D.-woman.HL-PL ‘the women of Domno (village)’ (*ñé-m*); *àná-óyò-n* village-chief.HL-SG ‘the chief of the village’ (*óyò-n*); *nùmó-gò:* hand-granary.HL ‘granary built by hand’ (*gò:*); *kú:n-dú:* head-load.HL ‘load carried on head’ (*dú:*).
- 3) Compounds of the type $\bar{X}\hat{V}_{PTCP}$ (Heath 2008: 197–198). This pattern is more productive and compositional than the above-described $\dot{N}\dot{V}_{PTCP}$. With respect to the semantic roles, the initial component is usually the theme/patient of the verb, but can be an instrument or a scene-setting spatio-temporal noun. Cf. *àsègè dígè-n* animal follow.HL-PTCP.SG ‘one who follows animals’ (*dígè*); *ù-jùw^mó dánà-m* RDP-mouse hunt.HL-PTCP.PL ‘mice hunters’ (*dánà-*); *jénéṅé dánà-n* metal.trap hunt.HL-PTCP.SG ‘trapper’; *dà:yá dánà-n* night hunt.HL-PTCP.SG ‘nighttime hunter’.
- 4) Bahuvrihi compounds of the type $\bar{N}\hat{A}$ (Heath 2008: 219–221). The initial component is a noun, the final component is an adjective or numeral. The whole is an adjective characterizing a person or entity by the denotatum of the initial noun modified by the adjective or numeral. Cf. *bèrè-dúgì-n* belly-fat.HL-SG ‘potbellied’ (*dúgù*); *kó:-gòni-n* leg-bent.HL-SG ‘bowlegged’ (*gòni*); *jìrè-túri-n* eye-one.HL-SG ‘one-eyed’ (*túri*).

The last three types of compounds have regular lexical tones on the initial component and a HL component contour on the final, which is reminiscent of inalienable possession NPs (see §7.1.4.8). For the bahuvrihi compounds, however, a parallel with relative clauses with Unaffixed Perfective participles (§7.1.4.10) may be more relevant.

Note that for the purposes of TDI calculation, I assume that there is no merge of tonemes across stem boundaries within compounds, e.g. the tonemic segmentation for *jìrè-túri-n* ‘one-eyed’ is [L jì.][H ré.][H tú.][L rì,-n] and not [L jì.][H ré.-tú.][L rì,-n].

7.1.4. Syntactically conditioned replacive tonal morphemes

7.1.4.1. Syntactically conditioned L toneme on core NPs

Several types of postpositional adnominal modifiers, namely the demonstrative *núṅò*, the universal quantifier *ká:n*, adjectives and relative clauses trigger a replacive L toneme on their nominal head. Cf. *ìjú* ‘dog’, but *ìjú núṅò* ‘this/that dog’, *ìjú ká:n* ‘any dog’, *ìjú jém* ‘black dog’

(Heath 2008: 231). In fact, the tonal span of the L toneme includes not just the head noun, but also its modifiers such as a numeral or an inalienable possessor:

- (36) a. *sáydu dèrè*
 S brother.HL¹⁷
 ‘Seydou’s brother’
- b. *sáydu dèrè làgí-n*
 S.L brother.L other-SG
 ‘Seydou’s other brother’
- c. *sáydu dèrè núwⁿò-n kùⁿ*
 S.L brother.L die.PFV.HL-PTCP.SG DEF
 ‘the brother of Seydou who died’ (Heath 2008: 233)

- (37) a. *mì dè: nérⁿè kúròy kùⁿ*
 1SG.P father.HL aunt.HL six DEF
 ‘my father’s six paternal aunts’
- b. [*mì dè: nérⁿè kúròy*] *nùhò-nám*
 1SG.P father.L aunt.L six DEM-HUM.PL
 ‘these/those six paternal aunts of my father’s’ (Heath & McPherson 2013: 291)

When the head of a relative clause is a conjoined NP (with no markers of conjunction other than the dying quail intonation described in §3.2.3.2), the L tonal morpheme imposed by the relative clause can only surface on the second conjunct, see example (4) and its discussion above.

When two or more tone-controlling modifiers follow the same noun (which is, for various reasons, uncommon in naturally occurring data), only the last one retains its lexical tones, while those preceding it surface all-L:

- (38) *ijù jèm dùgú*
 dog.L black.L big
 ‘a big black dog’ (Heath 2008: 245)

The question naturally arises whether tone-dropping proceeds cyclically, with each tone controller imposing its own L tonal morpheme on the preceding word, or whether the rightmost controller imposes a single L tonal morpheme on all the preceding elements of the core NP. This is especially relevant for TDI computation, because the answer determines the number of tonemes within the NP ([L *ijù*] [L *jèm*]... vs. [L *ijù jèm*]).

Heath (2008: 245) admits that the issue can not be decided empirically. However, a later paper (McPherson & Heath 2016), drawing on data from several Dogon languages, strongly advocates the latter approach. The authors go as far as to postulate that a tonal morpheme imposed on a word deletes not only its lexical tones, but also any tonal morphemes associated with it, so a controller on which a tonal morpheme has been imposed by another controller loses its own controlling status (Ibid.: 606). They also contend that no analysis assuming cyclic application of replacive àgrammatical tones upon attachment of each modifier can account for the Dogon data, presenting instead an OT framework where all tonal morphemes are introduced and evaluated in one step.

Specifically for Jamsay, the main argument for postulating a single L tonal morpheme in cases like (38) is provided by examples like (36b) and (37b). If a tonal morpheme generally affects a whole nominal projection c-commanded by its trigger, there’s no apparent reason why its span should be limited to one word in case of an intervening adjective.

However, straightforward adoption of this approach is not unproblematic. When a relative clause is followed by *nùhò* DEM, *ká:ⁿ* ‘any, all’ or (rarely) the adjective *làyá* ‘other’ (other tone controllers appear before or, more precisely, inside the relative), a tonal change attributable to the presence of this postpositional modifier is only observed on the participle, not on the whole relative clause:

¹⁷ The HL melody on ‘brother’ is a tonal morpheme marking inalienably possessed nouns, see §7.1.4.8 below.

- (39) *inè* *nîm* *bíré* *bîr-à:rà-n* *kâ:n* *kò:-r'ó*
 person.L now work_N work_V-PROG-PTCP.SG.L any be.NHUM-NEG
 ‘There is noone who is working now.’ (Heath 2008: 505)

In (39), the progressive participle *bîr-à:rà-n* ‘who is working’ has L tones on all TBUs, as does *inè* ‘person’ (but the latter would do so anyway as the head of a relative clause, even without *kâ:n*). However, the intervening *nîm* ‘now’ and *bíré* ‘work’ (which are also obviously within the c-command domain of the universal quantifier) retain their lexical tones. Thus, postulating the same L toneme on the head noun and the participle would violate the Continuity Criterion.

Moreover, when a participle contains the (textually rare) suffixal combination -PROG=NEG, the L tonal morpheme imposed by the following quantifier or demonstrative is realized on the Negative marker, with the rest of the stem to the left of it remaining intact (40a), (40c) vs. (40b). This is to be expected, given what is known about the negation of suffixed imperfective verbs with =*lá* (see §7.1.2 above)¹⁸.

- (40) a. [*kó* *bèrê:*] [*cè:* *bé:-rà=là-Ø* *kâ:n*] *kò:-r'ó*
 NHUM in thing.Lhappen-PROG=NEG.L-PTCP.NHUM any be.NHUM-NEG
 ‘In that domain (=legal disputes), there is nothing that doesn’t happen (=i.e., anything can happen).’ (Heath 2008: 371)
- b. *inè* *nîm* *pérù* *pèr-à:rà-n* *kâ:n* *kò:-r'ó*
 person.L now clap_N clap_V-PROG-PTCP.SG.L any be.NHUM-NEG
 ‘There is noone who is clapping now.’
- c. *inè* *nîm* *pérù* *pér-á:rà-n=là* *kâ:n* *kò:-r'ó*
 person.L now clap_N clap_V-PROG-PTCP.SG=NEG.L any be.NHUM-NEG
 ‘There is noone who is not clapping now.’ (Jeffrey Heath, p.c.)

As a technical solution, I assume that the L toneme imposed on a relative clause by a higher tone controller is realized on the participle (or the Negative marker if the participle contains the -PROG-NEG sequence) and blocked from spreading further leftwards. Thus, both (39) and (40) contain two replacive tonal morphemes, each with its own L toneme. In all other cases, a NP is considered to exhibit a single L toneme, triggered by the rightmost tone controller.

It yet remains to be seen whether the same effect as in relative clauses is observed in adjectival phrases. Adjectives in Jamsay can be expanded by means of *èjín* ⇒ ‘very’, *gá:rá* ‘more’ (cf. §7.1.4.8 below) or various (reduplicative) intensifiers (cf. §7.1.4.4). Neither (Heath 2008) nor (Heath 2019) provide any examples with noun phrases like ‘any two bigger houses’ or ‘those three snow-white goats’, so it is not clear if in such cases the L toneme triggered by the determiner/quantifier only affects the adjective or its modifiers as well.

7.1.4.2. Syntactically conditioned L toneme on personal pronouns

Personal pronouns in Jamsay often have their syntactic function distinguished by tone. The core of the pronominal system is given in Table 4:

	independent	subject	dative	alienable possessor	inalienable possessor
1SG	<i>mí</i>	<i>mì</i>	<i>mĩ-n</i>	<i>má</i>	<i>mì</i>
2SG	<i>ú</i>	<i>ù</i>	<i>ù-rú</i>	<i>á</i>	<i>ù</i>
3SG	<i>wó</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>wò-rú</i>	<i>wó</i>	<i>wò</i>
NHUM	<i>kó</i>	<i>kò</i>	<i>kò-rú</i>	<i>kó</i>	<i>kò</i>
1PL	<i>émé</i>	<i>èmè</i>	<i>émé-n</i>	<i>émé</i>	<i>èmè</i>
2PL	<i>é</i>	<i>è</i>	<i>è-rú</i>	<i>é</i>	<i>è</i>
3PL	<i>bé</i>	<i>bè</i>	<i>bè-rú</i>	<i>bé</i>	<i>bè</i>

Table 4. Basic personal pronouns (adopted from (Heath 2008: 156))

¹⁸ However, there seems to be some variation in this regard, both inter- and intra-speaker, and further investigation is desirable.

The H-toned “independent” pronouns are used independently, as direct objects and as complements of postpositions (other than the Dative). Alienable possessor pronouns are sometimes subsumed under the same label in the grammar, although they have segmentally distinct forms for singular locutors. Free-standing subject pronouns are only used in (non-subject) relatives and some other types of subordinate clauses; in other syntactic contexts, the subject is cross-referenced on the verb by a toneless suffix. Subject pronouns are L-toned and are formally completely identical to those used for inalienable possessors. Dative pronouns are the only ones formed suffixally, with the suffixes bearing no resemblance to the postposition introducing nominal recipients¹⁹. They have a LH tonal melody which is consistent with the pronominal stem carrying the L toneme and the H toneme being supplied by the suffix.

Heath (2008: 156–157) acknowledges that the Jamsay pronominal system lends itself to different interpretations. Following what seems to be the solution primarily adopted in the grammar (the glossing is somewhat inconsistent throughout the volume), I assume that basic forms are H-toned and the L-toned forms for subject and inalienable possessor have their syntactic status marked by a replacive tonal morpheme L. Thus, all unsuffixed pronominal forms contain one toneme, but this toneme is lexical if it is H and grammatical, if L. Dative pronouns attach dedicated H-toned suffixes that trigger a replacive tonal morpheme L on the preceding pronominal stem, similar to the verbal markers discussed in §7.1.2. The forms for alienable possessor in 1SG and 2SG (historically, amalgamations with the genitive clitic *mà*, now only used with full NP possessors (Heath 2022: 710)) contain both a tonal morpheme and a segmental change.

7.1.4.3. Syntactically conditioned L toneme on adjectives in comparative constructions

In asymmetrical comparative constructions, predicative adjectives specifying the parameter of comparison may receive a L toneme. The triggering factors are the presence of degree modifier *gá:rà* ‘more, most’²⁰ and perhaps the standard marked by the postposition *sógò* ‘instead of’, rather than with the Dative (Heath 2008: 444–447):

- (41) a. *mí gá:rà èjù*
 1SG more good.L
 ‘I am better.’ (Heath 2008: 445)
- b. *wò sógò wò déré gùrù-Ø*
 3SG.L instead.of 3SG.P.L brother.HL long.L-3SG
 ‘His brother is taller than he (is).’ (Ibid.: 446)

The same tonal change is found in symmetrical comparatives with *jín* ‘like’:

- (42) *wó jín gùrù-m*
 3SG like long.L-1SG
 ‘I am as tall as he (is).’ (Ibid.: 449)

7.1.4.4. Syntactically conditioned L toneme on adjectives with intensifiers

Adjectives in Jamsay can attach specialized intensifiers, most of which are frozen reduplications in form, like e.g. *pará-pará* associated with *pírú* ‘white’ or *póyⁿ-póyⁿ* associated with *nôm* ‘sour, salty’ (Heath 2008: 245–248; 2019: 14). Such modifiers immediately follow the primary adjective, imposing a L toneme on it (43, 44a). With predicatively used adjectives there is also an alternative construction, with the possibility of intervening material and no tonal change, as in (44b):

- (43) [*ijù jèm kújú-kújú léy*] *é-sà-m*
 dog.L black.L black.INTNS two see-RES-1SG
 ‘I saw two jet black dogs.’ (Heath 2008: 246)

¹⁹ Full NPs combine with the dative-locative-instrumental preposition *lè* (Heath 2008: 288–289). The 1st person dative pronouns are most probably conventionalized apocopated forms with the original *-rú*, with the identity of the suffix further obscured by regular consonantal alternations (*mĩ-n* < **mĩ-rⁿ* < **mĩ-rⁿú* < **mĩ-rú* (Ibid.: 65)).

²⁰ On the tonal effect of *gá:rà* on adnominal adjectives, see §7.1.4.9 below.

- (44) a. *jèm* *kújú-kújú=kò*
 black.L black.INTNS=be.NHUM
 ‘It is jet black.’
- b. *jém=kò* *kújú-kújú*
 black=be.NHUM black.INTNS
 ‘It is jet black.’ (Ibid.: 245–246)

While in the latter case the intensifier behaves like a loose adverbial, in the former case its position and tone-controlling properties are identical to those of a higher adjective, compare (43) to (38). It yet remains to be seen if the superficial similarity betrays identity of structure; if this proves to be the case, the L tonal morpheme in question can be subsumed under that discussed in §7.1.4.1. However, the semantics suggests bracketing of the kind [dog [black jet.black]] rather than [[dog black] jet.black]. Also, if such an analysis is to be extended to cases like (44a), one needs to posit an underlying nominal structure in adjectival predication (‘It is a jet black one’). Alternatively, it can be the case that (44a) features a different tonal morpheme L, the one covered in the preceding subsection. Again, a more thoroughful investigation into degree semantics and the syntax of comparatives in Jamsay is required in order to pursue this possibility. Yet another possibility, actually argued for in (Heath 2019: 15–16), is that an adjective and its intensifier form a compound, with the initial component receiving a L toneme. Evidence in favor of this conclusion comes from the reluctance of intensified adjectives to attach human number suffixes, as in (45b):

- (45) a. *ì-n* *ògí-n* *yé* *jìnè-m*
 child-HUM.SG.L fast-HUM.SG EXIST hold.PFV.L-1SG
 ‘I have a fast child (with me).’
- b. *ì-n* *ògù-táw-táw* *wò-n* *yé* *jìnè-m*
 child-HUM.SG.L fast.L-fast.INTNS be.HUM.HL-HUM.SG EXIST hold.PFV.L-1SG
 ‘I have a blazing fast child (with me).’ (Heath 2019: 15)

There is no corresponding asterisked example cited in (Heath 2019) (and (45a,b) is not a perfect minimal pair), but the idea is that the sequence ^{??}*ògù-n táw-táw* is unacceptable (or, at least, strongly dispreferred). If the compounding analysis is adopted, the L toneme on the adjective is imposed by another stem-level derivational tonal morpheme like those listed in (§7.1.3.2).

7.1.4.5. Syntactically conditioned L toneme on single numerals

Numerals 2–5 are all monosyllables intrinsically bearing a LH combination of tonemes: *lěy* ‘2’, *tǎ:n* ‘3’, *náyⁿ* ‘4’, *nú.yⁿ* ‘5’. When used NP-finally after a nominal head, they have their tone dropped to L, contrast (46b) to (46a, c):

- (46) a. *lěy* *é-sà-m*
two see-RES-1SG
 ‘I saw two (of them).’
- b. [*úró* *lěy*] *é-sà-m*
 house **two** see-RES-1SG
 ‘I saw two houses.’
- c. [*úró* *lěy* *kìⁿ*] *é-sà-m*
 house **two** DEF see-RES-1SG
 ‘I saw (the same) two houses.’ (Heath 2008: 184)

The numeral roots in question also undergo this tone drop in the same context as second components of decimal numerals, e.g. *pél-lěy* → *pél-lèy* ‘20’.

Unlike Tone Dissimilation in decimal numerals (see (§7.1.3.1), this tone change is not formulated by Heath (2008) as a separate tonal rule in the Phonology chapter, instead being covered in the section on numerals. However, it is relevant for our purposes: since the LH tone pattern in small numerals is viewed as a combination of two tonemes, the Tone Drop decreases the overall number of tonemes, while retaining all segmental units, thus decreasing the TDI. It also doesn’t seem to follow from any other tonal rule(s) of the language.

7.1.4.6. Replacive L tonal morpheme on defocalized predicates in main clauses

The Unsuffixed Perfective (Heath 2008: 344–347) is a verb form without any overt aspect-polarity suffixes bearing a L toneme. It is used in positive, semantically perfective main clauses when the verb undergoes defocalization. This includes the following cases:

- There is a focalized constituent that doesn't include the verb; it is usually (47a–b), but not necessarily (47c) marked with the focus clitic:

- (47) a. [ìjù núnò]=yⁿ **làyà-m**
 dog.L DEM=FOC hit.PFV.L-1SG
 'It is that dog_{FOC} that I hit.'
- b. yǎ:-jìn=i: dǎyǎ-m kó **cèjè-bà**
 how=FOC Dogon-PL NHUM.O welcome.PFV.L-3PL
 'How_{FOC} did the Dogon receive it (=the plow)?'
- c. **tàrá** yá: bè gá: kân dùn-yàrá **gò:-Ø**
 collective.hunt go 3PL.S.L say after lion go.out.PFV.L-3PL
 'When they (hunters) had gone out to the hunt, a lion_{FOC} appeared.'
- (Heath 2008: 345)

- The perfective viewpoint is evident from context and thus doesn't require explicit marking on the verb; such forms are common in narratives retelling complex events:

- (48) **pùlò-n** àsègè-jiré-n yè:-lé: yèré
 Fulbe-SG.L animal.L-tend.H-PTCP.SG there come
mèyⁿ, wó tèmè-Ø
 and 3SG.O find.PFV.L-3SG
 '(While he was working in the field,) A Fulbe herder came there and encountered him.'
- (Heath 2008: 346)

- The verb is the semantically light quotative (quasi-)verb following a quote:

- (49) **iné-m** [émé gá:-ná bèré-bà] **jè-Ø**
 person-PL 1PL.O go.past-CAUS can.IPFV.L-3PL.S say
 'Some people said they could take us across (the border).'
- (Heath 2008: 431)

The same tonal morpheme is found on other defocalized predicates, e.g. predicated adjectives:

- (50) a. á:=y **gùrù**
 who=FOC long.L
 'Who_{FOC} is long (=tall)?'
- b. wó=y **gùrù**
 3SG=FOC long.L
 'It's he/she_{FOC} who is long (=tall).'
- c. yǎ:-jìn **gùrù-w**
 how=FOC long.L-2SG.S
 'How_{FOC} long (=tall) are you?' (Heath 2008: 433)

7.1.4.7. Replacive H tonal morpheme for implicit possessor

In the nominal construction of inalienable possession, the possessed noun receives a HL tonal morpheme (see next subsection). However, parental terms *dě*: 'father' and *nǎ*: 'mother' also have special H-toned forms that appear when the possessor is presupposed but left unexpressed. These forms also take human number suffixes, unlike most kinship terms, which combine with the pluralizer *bé* instead.

	absolute	with overt possessor, SG	with overt possessor, PL	with implicit possessor, SG	with implicit possessor, PL
‘father’	<i>dě:</i>	<i>dê:</i>	<i>dê: bé</i>	<i>dê:-n</i>	<i>dê:-m</i>
‘mother’	<i>nâ:</i>	<i>nâ:</i>	<i>nâ: bé</i>	<i>nâ:-n</i>	<i>dâ:-m</i>

Table 5. Forms of parental terms (Heath 2008: 143)

In the following example, the word for ‘mother’ is first used in the ordinary possessed form, establishing the referent, then in the suffixal form, to refer to the same referent without invoking the possessor:

- (51) *wò nâ: mà pènê: wó dàyá-bà,*
 3SG.P.L mother.HL POSS beside 3SG.O leave.IPFV-3PL.S
nâ:-n kùⁿ=yⁿ wó jèrê:-Ø
 mother.H-SG DEF=FOC 3SG.O hold.IPFV-3SG.S
 ‘{They would excise her.} They would leave her at the side of her mother. The mother_{FOC} will hold her.’ (Heath 2008: 143)

7.1.4.8. Replacive HL tonal morpheme on inalienably possessed kinship nouns

Jamsay manifests (in)alienability distinction in the domain of nominal possession. In the unmarked construction (Heath 2008: 234–236), a nominal possessor (unless ending in the plural marker *bé* of pronominal origin) is divided from the possessor by the particle *mà*, while pronominal possessor appears in the H-toned form (see Table 4 above). There is no other tonal change.

- (52) *má ijú mà kó:*
 1SG.P dog POSS foot
 ‘my dog’s foot (=paw)’ (Heath 2008: 242)

A small set of inalienably possessed nouns requires another construction, with no intervening *mà*, L-toned form of a pronominal possessor and a HL tonal morpheme on the possessum (Heath 2008: 236–240):

- (53) a. *mì dê:*
 1SG.P.L father.HL
 ‘my father’
 b. *séydù dê:*
 Seydou father.HL
 ‘Seydou’s father’ (Heath 2008: 237)
 c. *mì dê: nérⁿè*
 1SG.P.L father.HL aunt.HL
 ‘my father’s aunt’ (*dê:* ‘father’; *nérⁿè* ‘paternal aunt’) (Ibid.: 240)

Composite kinship terms ending in ‘man’ or ‘woman’ have the HL tonal morpheme realized only on the initial (Heath 2008: 206, 239):

- (54) a. ‘grandmother’: *tìrè-ñě-n* (unpossessed) *tírè- ñě-n* (possessed)
 b. ‘grandfather’ *tìrè-ǎ-n* (unpossessed) *tírè-ǎ-n* (possessed)

The set of inalienably possessed nouns comprises most kinships terms plus *báɲà* ‘master (of slave)’, *tě:ⁿ* ‘friend’ and *tówⁿó* ‘comrade’, the latter of which also has alienably possessed forms. The abstract noun *cé* ‘possession’, which functions as a dummy head when no lexical noun is specified as the possessum, shows mixed behaviour: it takes possessors in the inalienable form (e.g., without *mà* and L-toned if pronominal), but doesn’t take the HL tonal morpheme²¹.

²¹ Being a defective grammatical noun, *cé* also violates the condition that requires all lexical stems to be at least bimoraic. It would have to undergo Contour-Tone Mora-Addition in order to accommodate the HL contour. The fact that this doesn’t happen is distantly reminiscent of the situation in Tommo So, where the tonal morpheme imposed by a pronominal possessor on an inalienably possessed noun is HL if said noun contains three or more morae, but is simplified to just H if it is bimoraic (McPherson 2013: 109, 190–191; McPherson & Heath 2016: 598).

7.1.4.9. Replacive HL tonal morpheme on adjectives with degree modifiers

Adnominal adjectives receive a HL tonal morpheme when accompanied by degree modifiers *èjín* ⇒ ‘very’ (Heath 2008: 304–305) or *gá:rà* ‘more, most’ (Ibid.: 444–445):

- (55) *ùrò* *èjín* ⇒ *éjù* *lèy* *jìnè-m*
house.L very good.HL two have.PFV.L-1SG
‘I have two very good houses.’ (Ibid.: 305)
- (56) *lì-lù:rò* *gá:rà* *dùgù* *gá:rà* *móñù*
RDP-snake.L more big.HL more bad.HL
‘the biggest, nastiest snake’ (*dùgù* ‘big’, *móñù* ‘bad’) (Ibid.: 445)

This tonal change only occurs within an NP; the degree modifiers in question have no effect on the tones of predicatively used adjectives (see §7.1.4.3 above for the case of *gá:rà*). It also provides a counter-example to the previously mentioned generalization made in (McPherson & Heath 2016: 606) for Dogon languages in general, namely that no word can simultaneously have its lexical tones substituted by a tonal morpheme and impose its own tonal morpheme on other words. In examples like (55)–(56), the adjective receives a HL tonal morpheme from its degree modifier, but still triggers a L toneme on the head noun.

7.1.4.10. Replacive HL tonal morpheme on participles

In positive perfective relative clauses (and other constructions based on relatives), participles generally appear without overt perfectivizing suffixes (Heath 2008: 497–500). They receive a replacive HL tonal morpheme:

- (57) a. *lùgù* *ù* *bàrá* *jâ:-Ø* *kùⁿ*
manure.L 2SG.S.L gather convey.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM DET
‘the manure that you have gathered and taken (there)’ (*jâ:* ‘convey’)
(Heath 2008: 498)
- b. *inè-m* *lè* *gó:* *túmnò-m*
person-PL.L INSTR dance_N begin.PFV.HL-PTCP.PL
‘the people with whom the dance will begin’ (*túmnò* ‘begin’) (Ibid.: 493)

Cf. the replacive L tonal morpheme on Unaffixed Perfective verbs in main clauses (§7.1.4.6). This is the only case in Jamsay when a finite verb form and a corresponding participle differ in their tonal make-up.

When a verbal chain (see the next subsection) is relativized, as in (57a) above, only the final verb appears in the participial form; the others surface as bare stems with their lexical tones.

Suffixed perfective participles are also attested in texts, but are very rare. They have a regular tonal pattern, cf. *nǎ:-jè-n* drink-RECPERF-PTCP.SG ‘the one who has drunk’ (Heath 2008: 495).

The same HL tonal morpheme appears on participialized adjectives:

- (58) a. *àná* *ní:* *lè* *é:ŋ*
village.L water in near.HL
‘the village that is near the water’ (*é:ŋ* ‘near’) (Heath 2008: 250)
- b. *sà:j-í:ⁿ*, [*dí:ⁿ* *kò* *téyⁿ·:* *fú:⇒*]
bird-child manner.L NHUM.S.L small.HL all
à-tí: *kó* *á:=kò*
bird.trap NHUM.O catch.IPFV=be.NHUM
‘A bird, however small it may be, a bird trap will catch it.’ (*téyⁿ* ‘small’)
(Ibid.: 500)

7.1.5. Replacive tonal morphemes in verb chains and iterations

7.1.5.1. Replacive L tonal morpheme on medial chained verbs

Jamsay makes ample use of VP-chaining (Heath 2008: 520ff), wherein several same-subject VPs (possibly reduced to simple verbs) are combined, with only the final verb being inflected for

aspect, negation and/or subject cross-reference, the rest appearing as bare stems. This probably covers a range of phenomena with various degrees of integration, from conjunction of two separate VPs standing in a temporal or causal relationship to each other to something more akin to verb-verb compounding. In this analytical report, I stick to Heath’s term (“VP-/verb chain(ing)”), avoiding the discussion of how well the Jamsay data conform to any of the existing definitions of a “serial verb construction”.

When three or more verbs are chained together in this manner without any intervening material, all verbs aside from the first and the last one optionally receive a L toneme:

(59) *sùrgǔ-n* *lè* *dé:* ***jà:*** *ó-bà*
 weaver-SG DAT carry take.L give.IPFV-3PL
 ‘They will carry it (=cotton) and give it to the weaver.’ (*jǎ:-*) (Heath 2008: 521)

(60=6) *nîŋ* *èné* *wó* *tá:ⁿ* ***wǔ:*** ***tí*** *yá:̃* *wàŋ*
 now LOG 3SG.O shoot kill.L LINK.L go.IPFV say
 ‘He said: “Now I will shoot and kill you and (then) go.”’ (*wǔ:-, tí*) (Ibid.)

As shown in (60) (previously cited in §4.1.1 as (6)), the linker *tí* falls within the tonal span of the L toneme in question just like any chained verb would, justifying its analysis as a defective verb. The same may also be true for another VP-combining device, the particle/conjunction *mèyⁿ* (Heath 2008: 521, 532–533), but its tonal behavior is less well understood.

Heath (Ibid.: 439–442) also dedicates a whole subsection to verb iteration, which can be viewed as a special subtype of chaining where all combined verbs (or all save the last one) are repetitions of the same verb. The most common pattern involves three verbs, of which the first two must be identical, while the final (the one bearing inflection) may be different. In this case, the second verb receives a L toneme:

(61) a. *ñě-m* *àrⁿ-úm* *nàná-nàná* *tàrá* *tí:-bà*
 woman-PL man-PLchase-chase.L collective.hunt send.IPFV-3PL
 ‘The women drive (=incite) and send men on the collective.hunt.’
 b. *háyé* *èné* *wó* *jìñé-jìñé-jìñé-sa* *jè*
 well LOG.S 3SG.O sniff-sniff.L-sniff.RES say.PFV.L
 ‘It (=Hyena) said, “well, I have sniffed and sniffed at you_{SG}”.’ (Heath 2008: 440)

This tonal change is consistent with the rule formulated above for VP-chains in general. (It seems like assignment of the L toneme is likewise optional, but Heath’s wording in this regard is a bit murky). I assume that the L tonal morpheme present in verb iterations in (61a–b) is the same as the one illustrated in (59)–(60).

7.1.5.2. Replacive L and HL tonal morphemes in verb iterations

A more distinctive iteration pattern identified in (Heath 2008: 440–442) involves from two to four repeated verb stems with no inflection whatsoever. Despite lack of inflection, such complexes are able to function as finite verbs²². In this configuration, the first verb appears HL-toned, while all subsequent ones appear L-toned:

(62) ...*sáŋá:-Ø* *sárá* *gàrá* ***kúnò-kúnò-kúnò*** *yǎ:*
 put.fence.IPFV-3SG.S pass pass put.HL-put.L-put.L go
 fútúró *mà* *wàkàtì* *núnò* *dó:-yè-Ø* *dèy*
 twilight POSS time.L DEM arrive-PFV-3SG.S if
 [*sáŋà-rⁿà*]-[*sàŋà-rⁿà*] *kó* *dìgé* *pílíwé:-Ø*
 put.fence-REV.HL-put.fence-REV.L NHUM.O follow return.IPFV-3SG.S

²² Both iterative complexes in (62) have a 3SG subject, which has a zero agreement marker. However, such iterated forms without an overt subject cross-reference are used with all other person-number combinations as well.

‘...he (=the trapper) encloses (traps) in fences; he goes by setting (traps within fences); then when twilight arrives, he goes back to them one by one and removes the fences.’ (*kúnó-, sájá-r^a-*) (Heath 2008: 441)

As testified by the second iterated form in the example above, the HL contour on the initial stem has unique association properties. In all other cases, the final L of the HL contour, whether lexical or grammatical, docks to the final mora of the stem, in accordance with the general tendency to place toneme transitions closer to the right edge (cf. §4.2). Here, on the contrary, the initial H toneme docks to the first mora, while the L toneme spreads over the rest of the stem.

This pattern also does not readily lend itself to a straightforward account in tonemic terms. Where shall tonal span boundaries in forms like *kúnò-kùnò-kùnò* put.HL-put.L-put.L be put? There are at least three logical possibilities:

- (63) a. [H *kú*][L *nò-*][L *kùnò-*][L *kùnò*]
 b. [H *kú*][L *nò-*][L *kùnò-kùnò*]
 c. [H *kú*][L *nò-kùnò-kùnò*]

The choice is relevant for TDI calculation, but there are no empirical grounds to prefer one solution over another. I tentatively go for option (b), which is sort of a middle ground.

Given its distinctive morphosyntactic and tonological properties, the construction discussed in this subsection should obviously be treated as a grammaticalized pattern of verb stem reduplication (including tri- and quadruplication) most akin to compounding and not a VP-level phenomenon.

7.2. Tonal paradigms

In Jamsay, personal pronouns (cf. §7.1.4.2) and inalienable kin terms (§7.1.4.8, also §7.1.4.7) can be argued to form tonal paradigms.

7.3. Lexical tones

Jamsay has lexical tones. The vast majority of morphemes host inherent tonemes.

Only a few clause-final function words are underlyingly toneless. They acquire tone by being included into the tonal span of the preceding mora, per Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading (§6.1.1). These include the conditional *dey*, the interrogative/disjunctive *ma* and the quotative *wa* (although the tonal outlook of the first two is often obscured by intonation effects).

7.4. Toneless morphemes

In addition to the above-listed function words, a few (monosyllabic or monomoraic) suffixes are underlyingly toneless. They acquire tone by being included into the tonal span of the preceding mora, per Atonal-Morpheme Tone-Spreading (§6.1.1).

The relevant syllabic suffixes are verbal inflections *-be* 2PL, *-ba* 3PL and nominal human number markers in their postconsonantal allomorphs *-in* SG, *-um* PL (only used with adjectives, since no human-denoting nouns are C-final). Postvocalic variants of the same, *-n* SG, *-m* PL are moraic, but not syllabic; in certain cases the preceding toneme is shifted rather than spread unto them (Contour-Tone Stretching, §6.1.3).

8. Tonal classes of words

8.1. Differentiation of parts of speech by tone

Verb stems have a more limited inventory of lexical tonal melodies as compared to other word classes, cf. §4.2.

8.2. Tonal classes of words (beyond the parts of speech distinctions)

Not relevant.

9. Diachrony of tone

No full reconstruction of the Proto-Dogon tonal system is yet available. However, (Heath 2022) contains a detailed reconstruction of the emergence of replacive tonal morphemes within the NP for the Dogon languages. The account is primarily based on data from Jamsay, Najamba, Yanda Dom, Nanga and the Yorno So dialect of Toro So, but draws on information from almost all Dogon languages. (Heath 2020) also provides partial reconstruction of stem-level tones in core aspect-polarity forms of the verb.

10. Tonal notation

10.1. Presentation of tones in (local) linguistic tradition

The present analytical report uses largely the same notation (L/H, diacritics) as (Heath 2008).

10.2. Tonal notation in the writing

There is no established practical orthography for Jamsay. The orthography proposed by Jeffrey Heath does not mark tonal distinctions.

11. Calculation of the Tonal Density Index

The TDI has been calculated on the basis of “The Pullo and the Dogon farmer” (Heath 2008: 705–720), the second of the two sample texts from the grammar. This text is a narrative that contains large chunks of reported dialogue. It thus features a relatively large number of reportative markers, which, being inherently toneless, contribute towards a lower TDI.

The text is represented in standard horizontal format adopted in the present project. The first line employs the transcription used throughout (Heath 2008). The text is 776 phonological words long and contains 1150 syllables, 1549 morae and 1129 tonal spans. The syllabic TDI is thus **0.98** and the moraic TDI is **0.73**.

<i>ɔ̃ⁿhɔ̃ⁿ</i>	<i>wàrù-wára-n,</i>	<i>èjú</i>	<i>lé</i>
[L ɔ̃.][H hɔ̃,][L ɔ̃]	<[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]>	[L è.][H jú]	[H lé]
uh-ho!	farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG	field	in

<i>wáru</i>	<i>wát-tɔ̃ɔ̃</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>wô:-Ø</i>	<i>jé</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
[H wá.rú]	[L wá,][H t̃.][H t̃.][L ɔ̃ɔ̃]	<[L wò]>	<[H wó,][L ð-Ø]>	[H jé]	[L mè,ɔ̃]
farming	farm-IPFV	3SG.S.L	be.HUM.HL-PTCP.NHUM	say	and

<i>pùlò-n</i>	<i>àsègè-jírè-n</i>	<i>yè:-lé:</i>	<i>yèré</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
<[L pù.lò,-n]>	<[L à.sè.gè.-]><[H jí.ré,-n]>	[L yè,è.][H lé,é]	[L yè.][H ré]	[L mè,ɔ̃]
Pullo-SG.L	animal.L-tend.H-PTCP.SG	there	come	and

<i>wó</i>	<i>tèmè-Ø</i>
[H wó]	<[L tè.mè-Ø]>
3SG.O	find.PERF.L-3SG

‘Uh-huh! While a (Dogon) farmer was doing farm work in a field, a Pullo animal herder came there and encountered him.’

<i>wàrù-wára-n</i>	<i>kùⁿ,</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>mà</i>	<i>màlfâⁿ</i>	<i>ló:wó</i>
<[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]>	[L kù]	[L è.][H né]	[L mà]	[L mà,l.][H fǎ,][L à]	[H ló,ó.wó]
farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG	DEF	REFL	POSS	rifle	load

<i>mèyⁿ</i>	<i>îⁿ</i>	<i>kúnó</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>	<i>sún,</i>	<i>tégé</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
[L mè,ɔ̃]	[H í][L ì]	[H kú.nó]	[L mè,ɔ̃]	[H sú,][L ò]	[H té.gé]	[L mè,ɔ̃]
and	child	put	and	ear	sprinkle	and

<i>kó</i>	<i>sún</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>	<i>nèrⁿé</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
[H kó]	[H sú,][L ò]	[L kù]	[L nè.][H řé]	[L mè,ỹ]
NHUM.P	ear	DEF	rub	and

<i>wò-tùmò</i>	<i>kàná</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>túmò-Ø</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>
<[L wò.-tù.mò]>	[L kà.][H ná]	[L è.][H né]	<[H tú.][L mò-Ø]>	[L kù]
ridge.L	new	REFL	make.mound.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM	DEF

<i>wò-túmó</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>	<i>mána</i>
[L wò.-][H tú.mó]	[L kù]	[H má.][L ná]
ridge	DEF	on

<i>kó</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>táyⁿá</i>	<i>jéřé-Ø</i>	<i>jé</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
[H kó]	<[L wò]>	[H tá.ỹá]	<[H jé.][L rè-Ø]>	[H jé]	[L mè,ỹ]
NHUM.O	3SG.S.L	lay.out.in.sun	hold.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM	say	and

<i>wó</i>	<i>jé:n</i>	<i>mà</i>	<i>dĩ:ⁿ</i>
[H wó]	[H jé,é,n]	[L mà]	[L dĩ,][H í,]<[L ì]>
3SG.P	gear	POSS	place.LOC.HL

<i>púlò-n</i>	<i>yèré</i>	<i>wó</i>	<i>témè-Ø.</i>
[H pú.][L lò,-n]	[L yè.][H ré]	[H wó]	<[L tè.mè-Ø]>
Pullo-SG	come	3SG.O	find.PFV.L-3SG

‘The farmer loaded his rifle, put bullets in it, sprinkled the ear (=chamber latch) of the rifle (with gunpowder), and rubbed its ear; when he made a new ridge (of earth, in the field), as he laid it (=rifle) on the surface of the ridge near his (farming) gear, the Pullo came and encountered him.’

<i>wó</i>	<i>èjú</i>	<i>põ:</i>	<i>wá⇒,</i>	<i>ó:.</i>	<i>wà</i>
[H wó]	[L è.][H jú]	[L pò,][H ó	<i>wá</i>	[H ó:.]	<i>[L wà]</i>
3SG.S	field	greeting	say	greeting	say

‘He (Pullo) said, “you there, greetings in the field!” He (=Dogon:) replied, “you there, greetings!”’

<i>wó</i>	<i>ní:</i>	<i>ó:</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>nò:-m</i>	<i>wà</i>
[H wó]	[H ní,í]	[H ó,ó]	[L è.][H né]	<[L ò,ò,-m	<i>wà</i> >
3SG	water	give.IMP	LOG.S	drink-so.that	say

‘He (=Pullo) said, “you there, give (me) some water so that I may drink!”’

<i>wáru</i>	<i>jèřé</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>wát-týğ</i>	<i>lè</i>
[H wá.rú]	<[L jè.řé]>	[L è.][H né]	[L wà,][H t.-][H tó.][L ýò]	[L lè]
farming	side.L	LOG.S	farm-IPFV	in

<i>èné</i>	<i>mà</i>	<i>ní:</i>	<i>wò-rú</i>	<i>sí:ré</i>	<i>té:ré</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
[L è.][H né]	[L mà]	[H ní,í]	<[L wò.-]>[H rú]	[H sí,í.ré]	[H té,é.ré]	[L mè,ỹ]
REFL	POSS	water	3SG-DAT	point	show	and

<i>èné</i>	<i>mà</i>	<i>ní:</i>	<i>yì-lé</i>	<i>yó=kò</i>	<i>gá</i>
[L è.][H né]	[L mà]	[H ní,í]	[L yì.-][H lé]	[H yó.=][L kò]	[H gá]
LOG	POSS	water	there	exist=be.NHUM	say

<i>wó</i>	<i>yǎ:</i>	<i>nó:</i>	<i>wá</i>
[H wó]	[L yà,][H á]	<[H nó,ó	<i>wá</i> >

3SG go drink.IMP say
 ‘At (=from) the spot where he (=Dogon) was farming, he (=Dogon) pointed out his (=Dogon’s) water to him (=Pullo), and said “my water is over there, you there, go and drink!”’

yǎ: *ní:* *ènέ* *nó:-Ø* *kùⁿ,*
 [L yǎ,][H á] [H ní,í] [L è.][H né] <[H nó,][L ò-Ø]> [L kù]
 go water REFL drink.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM DEF

wó *pìⁿé* *yó=kò* *gá,* *pìⁿé* *kùⁿ* *nè*
 [H wó] [L pì.][H řé] [H yó.][L kò] [H gá] [L pì.][H řé] [L kù] [L nè]
 3SG millet.cream exist=be.NHUM say millet.cream DEF now

yàṅá *nó:* *wá*
 [L yǎ.][H ṅá] <[H nó,ó wá]>
 take drink.IMP say

‘When he (=Pullo) had gone and drunk the water, he (=Dogon) said, “you there, there is some cream of millet; take and drink the cream of millet!”’

ó⇒ *wá,* *pìⁿé* *kùⁿ* *nè* *yàṅá* *mèyⁿ* *nò:-Ø.*
 [H ó wá] [L pì.][H řé] [L kù] [L nè] [L yǎ.][H ṅá] [L mè,ỹ] [L nò.ò-Ø]
 all.right say millet.cream DEF now take and drink.PFV.L-3SG
 ‘He (=Pullo) said, “all right!” He (=Pullo) took the cream of millet and drank (it).’

ènέ *nó:-Ø* *kùⁿ,*
 [L è.][H né] <[H nó,][L ò-Ø]> [L kù]
 REFL drink.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM DEF

wó *màlfā:ⁿ* *kùⁿ* *mà* *kú:ⁿ*
 [H wó] [L mà,í.][H fǎ,][L à] [L kù] [L mà] [H kú,][L ù]
 3SG.P rifle DEF POSS on

íjé *mèyⁿ,* *wàrù-wárá-n* *wá.*
 [H í,jé] [L mè,ỹ] <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n wá]>
 stand and farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG say

‘When he (=Pullo) had drunk, he (=Pullo) stood on his (=Dogon’s) rifle, and said “(hey) farmer!”’

hǎ:ⁿ *wá,* *hé,* *wó* *màlfā:ⁿ* *kùⁿ* *èjú=kò* *wá.*
 [L hǎ,][H á wá] [H hé] [H wó] [L mà,í.][H fǎ,][L à] [L kù] [L è.][H jú.][L kò wá]
 huh? say hey 3SG.P rifle DEF good=be.NHUM say

‘He (=Dogon) asked, “what?” He (=Pullo) said, “hey, your rifle is nice.”’

ní *wò* *gá:-Ø* *lè* *iré* *wá.*
 [H ní] <[L wò]> <[H gá,][L à-Ø]> [L lè] [L í.][H ré wá]
 here 3SG.S.L say.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM DAT be.better say

‘He (=Dogon) said, “it’s (even) better than what you (just) said.”’

ùró *mèyⁿ* *kó* *yàṅà-Ø.*
 [L ù.][H ró] [L mè,ỹ] [H kó] <[L yǎ.ṅà-Ø]>
 bend.over and NHUM.O take.PFV.L-3SG

‘He (=Pullo) bent over and picked it (=rifle) up.’

wó nújò yǒ: lé kó bèrè-Ø màŋ wàŋ.
 [H wó] [H nú.][L ŋò] [L yò,][H ó] [H lé] [H kó] <[L bè.rè-Ø mà wà]>
 3SG.S DEM where in NHUM.O get.PFV.L-3SG Q say

‘He (=Pullo) said, “you there, that (=rifle), where did you get it?”’

dì:ⁿ kó èné bèrè-Ø=y jé tègè-Ø.
 <[L dì,ì]> [H kó] [L è.][H né] <[H bé.][L rè-Ø=]>[L y] [H jé] <[L tègè-Ø]>
 place.L NHUM.O REFL get.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM ≡it.is say speak.PFV.L-3SG

‘He (=Dogon) said, “it’s where I got it.”’

wó nò màlfâ:ⁿ kùⁿ máné:-Ø,
 [H wó] [L nò] [L mà,1.][H fǎ,][L à] [L kù] [H má.né,]<[L è-Ø]>
 3SG.S now rifle DEF praise.IPFV-3SG

wó nò tégè:-Ø
 [H wó] [L nò] [H té.gé,]<[L è-Ø]>
 3SG.S now speak.IPFV-3SG

‘He (=Pullo) now, he was praising the rifle; he (=Dogon) now, he was talking.’

wó nò màlfâ:ⁿ kùⁿ máné:-Ø,
 [H wó] [L nò] [L mà,1.][H fǎ,][L à] [L kù] [H má.né,]<[L è-Ø]>
 3SG.S now rifle DEF praise.IPFV-3SG

wó nò tégè:-Ø
 [H wó] [L nò] [H té.gé,]<[L è-Ø]>
 3SG.S now speak.IPFV-3SG

‘He (=Pullo) now, he was praising the rifle; he (=Dogon) now, he was talking.’

hál màlfâ:ⁿ kùⁿ kúmó jè yèré
 [H há,][L ì] [L mà,1.][H fǎ,][L à] [L kù] [H kú.mó] [L jè] [L yè.][H ré]
 until rifle DEF hold.in.hand go.with come

wó dī:ⁿ dò:-Ø.
 [H wó] [L dī,][H í,]<[L ì]> <[L dò,ò-Ø]>
 3SG.P place.Loc.HL reach.PFV.L-3SG

‘Until, holding the rifle in his hand he (=Pullo) came and approached him (=Dogon).’

wó màlfâ:ⁿ kùⁿ kó tá:ⁿ=kò
 [H wó] [L mà,1.][H fǎ,][L à] [L kù] [H kó] [H tá,á=][L kò]
 3SG.P rifle DEF NHUM shoot.IPFV≡be.NHUM

èné mà:ná:-Ø wàŋ dé.
 [L è.][H né] [L mà.][H ná,]<[L à-Ø wà]> [H dé]
 LOG.S think.IPFV-3SG say Emph

‘He (=Pullo) said, “your rifle, I believe it will (=is ready to) fire.”’

inná:dilà:y
 [H ín.ná,á.][L dì.][H lá,][L à,y]
 by.God

ní wò gá:-Ø lè iré wá
 [H ní] <[L wò]> <[H gá,][L à-Ø]> [L lè] [L í.][H ré wà]
 here 3SG.S.L say.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM DAT be.better say

‘He (=Dogon) said, “by God, it’s better than what you (just) said.”’

kó bɛ̀ré lé cɛ̀: kún-Ø
 [H kó] [L bɛ̀.][H ré] [H lé] <[L cɛ̀,ɛ̀]> <[H kú,][L ñ-Ø]>
 NHUM.P inside in thing.L be.in.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM

ɛ̀né=ɣ̃ⁿ kó jùgô:.
 [L ɛ̀.][H né,=][L ɣ̃] [H kó] [L jù.][H gó,]<[L ò]>
 LOG≡FOC NHUM know.IPFV

‘He (Dogon) said “what is inside it, I focus am the one who knows.”’

kó sún tímné mèyⁿ, wǎ: dɛ̀:-nè-Ø.
 [H kó] [H sú,][L ñ] [H tí,m.né] [L mè,ɣ̃] [L wǎ,][H á] <[L dɛ̀,ɛ̀-nè-Ø]>
 NHUM.P ear close and pull.in sit-CAUS.PFV.L-3SG

‘He locked its (=rifle’s) ear (=gunpowder chamber latch) and pulled in and settled (it) (=closed the bolt).’

kó sún tímné mèyⁿ,
 [H kó] [H sú,][L ñ] [H tí,m.né] [L mè,ɣ̃]
 NHUM.P ear close and

wàrù-wára-n kùⁿ lè yàná dɛ̀:ré-Ø.
 <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]> [L kù] [L lè] [L yà.][H ná] <[L dɛ̀,ɛ̀.rè-Ø]>
 farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG DEF in take extend.PFV.L-3SG

‘He (=Pullo) locked its (=rifle’s) ear, and took it (=rifle) and held it out, pointing (it) at the farmer.’

wó màlfá:ⁿ kùⁿ mà bɛ̀ré:
 [H wó] [L mà,l.][H fá,][L à] [L kù] [L mà] [L bɛ̀.][H ré,][L ɛ̀]
 3SG.P rifle DEF POSS inside

cɛ̀: wò kùnò-Ø wó=ɣ̃ kó jùgô: wà.
 <[L cɛ̀,ɛ̀]> <[L wò]> <[L kù.nò-Ø]> [H wó,=][L ɣ̃] [H kó] [L jù.][H gó,]<[L ò] wà]>
 thing.L 3SG.S.L put.PFV.L-3SG 3SG≡FOC NHUM.O know.IPFV say

‘He (=Pullo) said, what you-Sg have put in your rifle, it’s you focus who knows it.’’

ɛ̀né wó èjú mà bɛ̀ré:
 [L ɛ̀.][H né] [H wó] [L ɛ̀.][H jú] [L mà] [L bɛ̀.][H ré,][L ɛ̀]
 LOG.S 3SG.P field POSS inside

wó ní: nǎ:-jè-Ø, wó pí^rè nǎ:-jè-Ø,
 [H wó] [H ní,i] [L nǎ,][H ó.-][L jè-Ø] [H wó] [L pí.][H rɛ̀] [L nǎ,][H ó.-][L jè-Ø]
 3SG.P water drink-RECPERF-3SG 3SG.P millet.cream drink-RECPERF-3SG

bónò-mójjérè wǒ-r kán tí yá:-Ø wà.
 [H bó.][L nò.-][H mó,j.jé.][L rɛ̀] <[L wò,-]>[H f] [H ká,n] [H tí] [L yà,][H á,]<[L à-Ø] wà]>
 ungratefulness 3SG-DAT do and go.IPFV-3SG say

‘He (=Pullo) said, “I have drunk your water in your field, I have drunk your cream of millet, (but) I will be ungrateful to you and leave.”’

<i>nīy</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>wó</i>	<i>tá:ⁿ</i>	<i>wò:</i>	<i>tì</i>	<i>yá:~Ø</i>	<i>wàŋ.</i>
[H ní,][L ò]	[L è.][H né]	[H wó]	[H tá,á]	<[L wò,ò]	tì>	[L yà,][H á,]<[L à-Ø]	wàŋ>
now	LOG.S	3SG.O	shoot	kill.L	LINK	go.IPFV-3SG	say

‘He (=Pullo) said, “now I will shoot and kill you and go.”’

<i>hâ:ⁿ</i>	<i>má</i>	<i>wá,</i>	<i>ɔⁿhóⁿ</i>	<i>wá.</i>
[H há,][L à]	[H má]	wá]	[L ò.][H hó]	wá]
huh?	Q	say	uh-huh	say

‘He (=Dogon) asked, “what?” He (=Pullo said, “uh-huh!”’

<i>èné</i>	<i>ámà</i>	<i>jé</i>	<i>wò-rú</i>	<i>jàŋà-Ø</i>	<i>wàŋ,</i>
[L è.][H né]	[H á.][L mà]	[H jé]	<[L wò.-]>[H rú]	<[L já.ŋà-Ø]	wàŋ>
LOG.S	God	PURP	3SG-DAT	beg.PFV.L-3SG	say

<i>wó</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>tá:ⁿ</i>	<i>wò:-y</i>	<i>wá.</i>
[H wó]	[L è.][H né]	[H tá,á]	<[L wò,ò,-]>[H y]	wá]
3SG	LOG.O	shoot	kill-PROH	say

‘He (=Dogon) said, I (hereby) beg you, for the sake of God, you there, don’t shoot and kill me!’”

<i>wó</i>	<i>cè:</i>	<i>tùrù</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>dènè:-Ø</i>	<i>cêw</i>	<i>tégé</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
[H wó]	<[L cè,è]>	<[L tù.rù]>	<[L wò]>	[H dé.né,]<[L è-Ø]>	[H cè,][L w]	[H té.gé]	[L mè,ÿ]
3SG	thing.L	one.L	3SG.S.L	want.IPFV-PTCP.NHUM	all	speak	and

<i>èné</i>	<i>wò-rú</i>	<i>kárⁿá-m</i>	<i>wá.</i>
[L è.][H né]	<[L wò.-]>[H rú]	[H ká.řá,-m]	wá]
LOG.S	3SG-DAT	do-so.that	say

‘He (=Dogon) said, “you there, (you) having said one thing that you wish, I will make it (happen) for you.”’

<i>cè:</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>dènè:-Ø.:</i>	<i>fú:</i>	<i>kò:-rò</i>	<i>jè-Ø,</i>
<[L cè,è]>	[L è.][H né]	[H dé.né,]<[L è-Ø]>	[H fú,ú]	<[L kò,ò.-]>[H ró]	<[L jè-Ø]>
thing.L	LOG.S	want.IPFV-3SG	all	be-NEG	say.PFV.L-3SG

<i>wó</i>	<i>wò-tùmò</i>	<i>nūŋò</i>	<i>mà</i>	<i>jìrè-dágù</i>	<i>yí-dì:ⁿ</i>
[H wó]	<[L wò.-tù.mò]>	[H nú.][L ò]	[L mà]	[L jì.rè.-][H dá.][L gù]	[H yí.-][L dì,ì]
3SG.S	ridge.L	DEM	POSS	front	there

<i>tórⁿó</i>	<i>mèyⁿŋ</i>	<i>bé:</i>	<i>bě:=y</i>	<i>là:</i>	<i>dèy.</i>
tóř	[L mè,ÿ]	[H bé,é]	<[L bē,]=>[H é,]=[L ÿ]	[L là,à]	dè,ÿ]
squat	and	excrement	defecate.MSD≡it.is	NEG	if

‘He (=Pullo) said, “there is nothing that I want,” he (=Pullo) said, “if it is not (=other than) that you squat there on the ridge (between furrows in the field) and defecate.”’

<i>wó</i>	<i>ámà</i>	<i>jè</i>	<i>kó</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>	<i>ké</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>lè</i>	<i>kàⁿà-yⁿ</i>	<i>wá,</i>
[H wó]	[H á.][L mà]	[H jé]	[H kó]	[L kù]	[H ké]	[L è.][H né]	[L lè]	<[L ká.řá,-]>[H ÿ]	wá]

3SG God PURP NHUM DEF TOP LOG DAT do-PROH say.

èné è:-ñèrⁿè-ýⁿ wá.
 [L è.][H né] <[L è,è.-ñè.řè,-]>[H ý wá]
 LOG.O humiliate-PROH say

'He (=Dogon) said, "you, for the sake of God, don't do (this) to me! Don't humiliate me!"'

wó kó kàn-lí èné wó tà:ⁿ-ýⁿ
 [H wó] [H kó] <[L kà,n.-]>[H lí] [L è.][H né] [H wó] <[L tà,à,-]>[H ý]
 3SG.S NHUM.O do-PFV.NEG LOG.S 3SG.O shoot-PROH

mà nàḡà-dùr^ó kò:-r^ó jè-Ø.
 [L mà] <[L nà.ḡà,-]>[L dù.][H r^ó] <[L kò,ò,-]>[H r^ó] <[L jè-Ø]>
 POSS cow.L-tail be-NEG say.PFV.L-3SG

'He (=Pullo) said, "(if) you don't do it, there is no cow-tail of "let me not shoot you."'

jèrè èné gò:-Ø wó jò:-gò-Ø⇒,
 <[L jè.rè]> [L è.][H né] [H gò,][L ò-Ø] [H wó] <[L jò,ò,-]>[H gò-Ø]
 side.L LOG.S go.out.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM 3SG.S know-IPFV.NEG-3SG

wó èné mà ná: jò:-gò-Ø⇒,
 [H wó] [L è.][H né] [L mà] [H ná,á] <[L jò,ò,-]>[H gò-Ø]
 3SG.S LOG POSS self know-IPFV.NEG-3SG

jèrè èné yã-Ø wó jò:-gò-Ø.
 <[L jè.rè]> [L è.][H né] [L yà,][H á,]<[L à-Ø]> [H wó] <[L jò,ò,-]>[H gò-Ø]
 side.L LOG.S go.IPFV-PTCP.NHUM 3SG.S know-IPFV.NEG-3SG

'(Pullo:) "The area where I have come from you don't know, me personally you don't know, the area where I am going you don't know."

èjú bérè=ý sǎy yèré èné wó tèmè-Ø,
 [L è.][H jú] [H bé.][L rè=][L sǎy] [L yè.][H ré] [L è.][H né] [H wó] <[L tè.mè-Ø]>
 field in=FOC only come LOG.S 3SG.O find.PFV.L-3SG

èné nīḡ wó tá:ⁿ wò: tì mèyⁿ yã-Ø wà.
 [L è.][H né] [H ní,][L wó] [H tá,á] <[L wò,ò] [L tì] [L mè,ý] [L yà,][H á,]<[L wà]>
 LOG.S now 3SG.O shoot kill.L LINK.L and go.IPFV-3SG say

'He (=Pullo) said, "it is only in (this) field that I have come and encountered you; now, after shooting and killing you, I will go."

wò-rú jàḡà-Ø, wò-rú èyⁿ-nè-Ø,
 <[L wò,-]>[H rú] <[L jà.ḡà-Ø]> [L wò,-][H rú] <[L è,ý,-nè-Ø]>
 3SG-DAT beg.PFV.L-3SG 3SG-DAT tighten-CAUS.PFV.L-3SG

nùḡò-bá:ⁿ wò-rú jàḡá:-Ø,
 <[L nù.ḡò,-]>[H bá,][L à] <[L wò,-]>[H rú] [L jà.][H ḡá,]<[L à-Ø]>

DEM.L-owner 3SG-DAT beg.IPFV-3SG

*nùŋò-bá:*ⁿ *nè* *wò-rú* *éyⁿ-nè:-Ø*
 <[L nù.ŋò.-]>[H bá,][L à] [L nè] <[L wò.-]>[H rú] [H é,ÿ.-nè,]<[L è-Ø]>
 DEM.L-owner now 3SG-DAT tighten-CAUS.IPFV-3SG

bé: *kùⁿ* *wó* *bè:-wé* *kàrà-Ø.*
 [H bé,é] [L kù] [H wó] [L bè,è.-][H wé] <[L kà.rà-Ø]>
 excrement DEF 3SG.O defecate-CAUS compel.PFV.L-3SG

‘He (=Dogon) pleaded with him, (but) he (=Pullo) put the squeeze (=pressure) on him; this one (=Dogon) was pleading with him, (but) this one (=Pullo) was putting the squeeze on him, (until) he compelled him to defecate.’

wó *ènè* *bé:-wè-Ø* *kùⁿ,* *mòwⁿó* *mèyⁿ,*
 [H wó] [L è.][H nè] <[H bè,è.-][L wé-Ø]> [L kù] [L mò.][H wó] [L mè,ÿ]
 3SG.S LOG.S defecate-CAUS.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM DEF laugh(v) and

wàrù-wára-n *li-lé:* *lòy-á:-Ø* *wà,*
 <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]> [L li.-][H lé,é] [H lò.y.á,][L à-Ø] *wà*
 farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG RDP-fear overflow-PFV-3SG say

jàkà-jàkà *wàrù-wára-n* *ké*
 [H já.][L kà.-][H já.][L kà] <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]> [H ké]
 lo! farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG TOP

cè: *wó* *jà:sé-sà-Ø.:* *fú:* *kò:-ró*
 <[L cè,è]> [H wó] [H já,á.sé.-][L sà-Ø] [H fú,ú] <[L kò,ò.-]>[H ró]
 thing.L 3SG.O be.worthless-RES-PTCP.NHUM all be.NHUM-NEG

‘When he had made him defecate, he (=Pullo) laughed: “lo, a farmer, (his) fearfulness overflows (=is excessive),” he said. “A farmer, there is nothing more shiftless (=cowardly) than him.”

ènè *wó* *èjú* *bérè* *yèré* *wó* *témé* *mèyⁿ*
 [L è.][H nè] [H wó] [L è.][H jú] [H bé.][L rè] [L yè.][H ré] [H wó] [H té.mé] [L mè,ÿ]
 LOG.S 3SG.P field in come 3SG.O find and

wó *ní:* *nǎ:-jè-Ø⇒,*
 [H wó] [H ní,í] [L nǎ,][H ó.-][L jè-Ø]
 3SG.P water drink-RECPERF-3SG

wó *pìrⁿé* *nǎ:-jè-Ø⇒,*
 [H wó] [L pì.][H r̃é] [L nǎ,][H ó.-][L jè-Ø]
 3SG.P millet.cream drink-RECPERF-3SG

wó *màlfā:*ⁿ *lè* *bé:* *wó* *bè:-wé-ti-Ø,*
 [H wó] [L mà,l.][H fá,][L à] [L lè] [H bé,é] [H wó] [L è,è.-][H wé.-][L ti-Ø]
 3SG.P rifle with excrement 3SG.O defecate-CAUS-PFV-3SG

<i>èné</i>	<i>ké</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>mà</i>	<i>dí:ⁿ</i>	<i>yǎ:-yè-Ø</i>	<i>wà.</i>
[L è.][H né]	[H ké]	[L è.][H né]	[L mà]	[L dĩ.][H í]	[L yà.][H á.][L yè-Ø]	wà]
LOG	TOP	LOG	POSS	place	go-PFV-3SG	say

‘(Pullo:) “having come into your field and encountered you, I drank your water, I drank your cream of millet, with your (own) rifle I made you defecate; as for me, I have gone (=I am off) to my place,” he said.

<i>màlfá:ⁿ</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>únò-Ø</i>	<i>kùⁿ,</i>
[L mà,l.][H fá.][L à]	[L kù]	[L è.][H né]	<[H ú.][L nò-Ø]>	[L kù]
rifle	DEF	LOG.S	put.down.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM	DEF

<i>jìgìré</i>	<i>mèyⁿ</i>	<i>kò-rú</i>	<i>gǔn</i>	<i>tò:-Ø</i>
[L jì.gì.][H ré]	[L mè,ỹ]	<[L kò.-]>[H rú]	[L gù.][H n]	<[L tò,ò-Ø]>
turn.around	and	NHUM-DAT	back	turn.PFV.L-3SG

‘When he (=Pullo) put the rifle down, he (=Pullo) turned around and turned his back to it (=rifle).’

<i>wò</i>	<i>yǎ:-Ø</i>	<i>jé</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
<[L wò]>	[L yà.][H á.][L à-Ø]>	[H jé]	[L mè,ỹ]
3SG.S.L	go.IPFV-3SG	say	and

<i>dáyà:</i>	<i>wó</i>	<i>tény:ⁿ⇒</i>	<i>gó:-yà-Ø</i>
[H dá.][L yà,à]	[H wó]	[H té.né,ỹ]	[L gò.][H ó.][L yà-Ø]
a.little	3SG.S	apart	go.out-PFV-3SG

<i>èné</i>	<i>ê:-Ø</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>
[L è.][H né]	<[H é.][L è-Ø]>	[L kù]
REFL.S	see.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM	DEF

<i>ǎ-n</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>ùró</i>	<i>mèyⁿ</i>
[L à.][H n]	[L kù]	[L è.][H né]	[L ù.][H ró]	[L mè,ỹ]
man-SG	DEF	REFL.S	bend.over	and

<i>èné</i>	<i>mà</i>	<i>màlfá:ⁿ</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>	<i>yàṅà-Ø.</i>
[L è.][H né]	[L mà]	[L mà,l.][H fá.][L à]	[L kù]	<[L yà.ṅà-Ø]>
LOG	POSS	rifle	DEF	pick.up.PFV.L-3SG

‘While he (=Pullo) man was going, when he (=Dogon) saw that he (=Pullo) had gone a short distance away, the (Dogon) man bent over and picked up his rifle.’

<i>dí:ⁿ</i>	<i>wǎ:</i>	<i>dè:-nè</i>	<i>tímné</i>	<i>mèyⁿ</i>
<[L dĩ.ĩ]>	[L wà.][H á]	<[L dè,è.-nè]>	[H tí,m.né]	[L mè,ỹ]
manner.L	pull.to.self	sit-CAUS	close	and

<i>dí:ⁿ</i>	<i>dàya</i>	<i>tí</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>yá:-Ø</i>	<i>jín</i>
<[L dĩ.ĩ]>	[L dà.][H yá]	[H tí]	<[L wò]>	<[H yá.][L à-Ø]>	[H jí,n]
manner.L	leave	LINK	3SG.S.L	go.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM	like

yàṅá wǒ-r dè:rè-Ø.
 [L yà.][H ṅá] [L wò,][H f] <[L dè,è.rè-Ø]>
 pick.up 3SG-DAT extend.PFV.L-3SG

‘Just as he (=Pullo) had pulled (the cock) toward himself, set it and closed it, as he (=Pullo) had left it (=rifle) and gone away, he (=Dogon) picked it up and held it out (ready to shoot).’

nàṅà-jírè-n wá há:n wá,
 <[L nà.ṅà.-]><[H jí.ré,-n wá]> [L há,][H á wá]
 cow.L-tend.H-PTCP.SG say huh? say

wó gònó yàṅá wá.
 [H wó] [L gò.][H nó] [L yà.][H ṅá wá]
 3SG.S turn look.IMP say

‘He (=Dogon) said: ‘Oh cowherd!’ He (=Pullo) said, “what?” He (=Dogon) said, “turn your head and look!”

gònó yàṅà-Ø,
 [L gò.][H nó] <[L yà.ṅà-Ø]>
 turn look.PFV.L-3SG

wó gòṅó lè dém-dém dè:ré tí dàyà-Ø.
 [H wó] [L gò.][H nó] [L lè] [H dé,m.-dé,m] [L dè,è.][H ré] [H tí] <[L dà.yà-Ø]>
 3SG.P chest in straight extend LINK leave.PFV.L-3SG

‘He (=Pullo) turned his head and looked. He (=Dogon) kept (the rifle) pointing straight at his (=Pullo’s) chest.’

nīṅ ké ñné=yⁿ wò-rú wàjà-Ø mà↑
 [H ní,][L ṅ] [H ké] [L ñ.][H ñé,=][L ý] <[L wò.-]>[H rú] <[L wà.jà-Ø mà]>
 now TOP what=FOC 3SG-DAT remain.PFV.L-3SG Q

wó jùgò:-Ø mà wà
 [H wó] [L jù.][H gó,]<[L ò-Ø mà wà]>
 3SG.S know.IPFV-3SG Q say

màlfá:n kùr èné kó dó:-jè-Ø gà,
 [L mà,l.][H fǎ,][L à] [L kù] [L è.][H né] [H kó] [H dó,ó.-][L jè-Ø] [L gà]
 rifle DEF LOG.S NHUM.O reach-RECPERF-3SG say

èné ké yì-dí:n bèr=í:
 [L è.][H né] [H ké] [L yì.-][H dí,][L ì] <[H bè.]>[H r=í,][L ì]
 LOG TOP there livelihood=it.is

èné mà dí:n=yⁿ wà,
 [L è.][H né] [L mà] [L dí,][H í=][L ý wà]
 LOG POSS place=it.is say

‘He (=Dogon) asked: “now, what is it that remains (=is in store) for you? Do you know? The The rifle, I have reached (=gotten to) it,” he said; “as for me, (my) livelihood is there, my place is there,” he said.

<i>dì.ⁿ</i> <[L ðǐ, ð̃]> place.L	<i>nîŋ</i> [H ní,][L ñ] this	<i>ní</i> [H ní] here	<i>èné</i> [L è.][H né] LOG	<i>wò:-Ø</i> <[L wò, ð-Ø]> be.PFV(HL)-PTCP.SG.L	<i>núnò</i> [H nú.][L ñò] DEM	<i>lè,</i> [L lè] in,
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<i>nîŋ</i> [H ní,][L ñ] now	<i>nèmné</i> [L nè,m.][H né] scorpion	<i>ǎ-n</i> [L à,][H n] man-SG	<i>tàŋà:</i> [H tá.][L ñà, à happen	<i>dèy</i> dè,y]> if
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<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.S	<i>lá:kàrà</i> [H lá,á.ká][L rà] hereafter	<i>jà:jé:-Ø</i> [H já,á.jé,]<[L è-Ø go.back.IPFV-3SG	<i>wà</i> wà]> say
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<i>èné=yⁿ</i> [L è.][H né=][L ÿ] LOG=FOC	<i>dì.ⁿ</i> <[L ðǐ, ð̃]> manner.L	<i>kò</i> [L kò] NHUM.S.L	<i>kárⁿá=kò</i> [H ká.řá.]=[L kò] do.IPFV=be.NHUM	<i>jùgò:</i> [L jù.][H gó,]<[L ð-Ø know.IPFV	<i>wà,</i> wà]> say
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‘(Dogon:) “In this place, here, in (the place) where I am, now if the trigger (“scorpion”) is a man (=is courageous), you will go back to the Hereafter (=will die),” he said; “it’s I focus who knows how it operates (=what it’s for),” he said.

<i>bé:</i> [H bé,é] excrement	<i>kùⁿ</i> [L kù] DEF	<i>mà</i> [L mà] POSS	<i>bè-y=y</i> <[L bè-]>[H ý=][L ÿ] defecate-MSD=FOC	<i>nàm=lá</i> <[L nà,m.=]>[H lá difficult=NEG	<i>wá</i> wá] say	<i>kòy,</i> [L kò,y] EMPH
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<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.S	<i>yèré</i> [L yè.][H ré] come	<i>bé:</i> [H bé,é] excrement	<i>kùⁿ</i> [L kù] DEF	<i>yàŋá</i> [L yà.][H ŋá] pick.up	<i>ñé:</i> <[H ñé,é eat.IMP	<i>wá,</i> wá]> say
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‘(Dogon:) “Defecating is indeed not difficult,” he said. “You, come and pick up and eat the excrement!” he said.’

<i>kó</i> [H kó] NHUM.S	<i>ìrè-Ø</i> <[L ì.rè-Ø]> be.better.PFV.L-3SG	<i>gá</i> [H gá] say	<i>dáyà:</i> [H dá.][L yà, à a.little
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<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.S	<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.P	<i>cíⁿé</i> [H cí.řé] nose	<i>kùⁿ</i> [L kù] DEF	<i>dènè:-Ø</i> [L dè.][H né,]<[L è-Ø want.IPFV-3SG	<i>dèy,</i> dè,y]> if
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<i>yèré</i> [L yè.][H ré] come	<i>bé:</i> [H bé,é] excrement	<i>kùⁿ</i> [L kù] DEF	<i>yàŋá</i> [L yà.][H ŋá] pick.up	<i>ñé:</i> <[H ñé,é]> eat.IMP
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<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.S	<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.P	<i>cíⁿé</i> [H cí.řé] nose	<i>kùⁿ</i> [L kù] DEF	<i>dènè-gó-Ø</i> [L dè.nè.-][H gó-Ø] want- IPFV.NEG-3SG	<i>tàŋà:</i> [H tá.][L ñà, à happen	<i>dèy,</i> dè,y] if
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<i>èné</i> [L è.][H né] LOG	<i>mà</i> [L mà] POSS	<i>wàrù-wàrù</i> <[L wà.rù.-wà.rù]> (active)field.L	<i>núnò</i> [H nú.][L ñò] DEM	<i>bère</i> [H bé.][L rè] in
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<i>èné</i>	<i>wó</i>	<i>ðwⁿð-sáyn</i>	<i>ja:ⁿ-Ø</i>
[L è.][H né]	[H wó]	[L ð.ðð-sà,][H ý]	[L já,][H á,]<[L à-Ø]>
LOG.S	3SG.S	grave	dig.IPFV-3SG

<i>wó</i>	<i>kúnó</i>	<i>bò:</i>	<i>tì</i>	<i>ya:ⁿ-Ø</i>	<i>wà.</i>
[H wó]	[H kúnó]	<[L bò,ð]	[L ti]>	[L yà,][H á,]<[L à-Ø]	[L wà]>
3SG.S	put	bury.L	LINK.L	go.IPFV-3SG	say

‘(Dogon:) “it’s better, somewhat” he said; “if you love your nose (=your life), come and pick up and eat the excrement; if it happens that you do not love your nose, I will dig your grave in this field of mine; I will put you down and bury you and go away,” he said.’

<i>tá:ⁿ</i>	<i>wò:</i>	<i>tì</i>	<i>mèyⁿ,</i>
[H tá,á]	<[L wò,ð]	[L ti]>	[L mè,y]
shoot	kill.L	LINK.L	and

<i>wó</i>	<i>nànyá</i>	<i>já:jé=kò=y</i>	<i>là:</i>	<i>dèy</i>
[H wó]	[L nà.][H nyá]	[H já,á.jé.][L kò,=][L ý]	[L là,à]	[L dè,y]
3SG.P	cow	go.back.IPFV ≡be.NHUM.S≡it.is	NEG	if

<i>jèrè</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>gò:-Ø</i>
<[L jè.rè]>	<[L wò]>	<[H gó,][L ò-Ø]>
side.L	3SG.S.L	go.out.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM

<i>jèrè</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>já:jé:-Ø</i>
<[L jè.rè]>	<[L wò]>	[H já,á.jé.][L è-Ø]>
side.L	3SG.S.L	go.back.IPFV-PTCP.NHUM

<i>inè</i>	<i>kó</i>	<i>jùgò-n</i>	<i>fú:</i>	<i>kò:-rò</i>	<i>wá.</i>
<[L inè]>	[H kó]	[L jù.][H gó,]<[L -n]>	[H fú,ú]	<[L kò,ò.-]>[H ró]	[L wá]
person.L	NHUM.O	know.IPFV-PTCP.SG	all	be.NHUM-NEG	say

‘(Dogon:) “(I) having shot and killed (you), other than (by the fact that) your cows are going back (from pasturing), where you have come from (and) where you are going back, there is nobody who will know,” he said.’

<i>èné=yⁿ</i>	<i>wó</i>	<i>wò:</i>	<i>mà⇒</i>	<i>ká:ⁿ</i>
[L è.][H né=][L ý]	[H wó]	<[L wò,ð]	[L mà]>	[H ká,][L à]
LOG≡FOC	3SG.O	kill.PFV	Q	too

<i>ijé</i>	<i>bòró</i>	<i>gò:-gò-Ø</i>	<i>táy=kò</i>	<i>wà,</i>
[H í.jé]	[L bò.][H ró]	<[L gò,ò.-]>[H gó-Ø]	[H tá,η.=][L kò]	[L wà]
today	rear.end	go.out-IPFV.NEG-3SG	happen.IPFV≡be.NHUM.S	say

<i>wó</i>	<i>nò</i>	<i>dì:ⁿ</i>	<i>èné</i>	<i>lè</i>	<i>wò</i>	<i>gá:-Ø</i>	<i>kùⁿ</i>	<i>jín,</i>
[H wó]	[L nò]	<[L dī,ī]>	[L è.][H né]	[L lè]	<[L wò]>	<[H gá,][L à-Ø]>	[L kù]	[H jí,n]
3SG	now	manner.L	LOG	DAT	3SG.S	say.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM	DEF	like

<i>yàṅá</i> [L yà.][H ṅá] pick.up	<i>èné</i> [L è.][H né] REFL.S	<i>mà</i> [L mà] POSS	<i>ká:</i> [H ká,á] mouth	<i>gòmó</i> [L gò.][H mó] open(tr)	<i>ñé:-sà-Ø</i> [H ñé,é.][L sà-Ø] eat-RES-3SG	<i>dèy,</i> if
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<i>héy</i> [H hé,y] eh!	<i>wàrù-wàrà-n</i> <[L wà.rù.-wà.rà,-n]> farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG	<i>nì-bâ:ⁿ</i> <[L nì.-]>[H bá,][L à̃] this.L-owner	<i>mà</i> [L mà] POSS	<i>bé:</i> [H bé,é] excrement
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<i>ér=kò</i> [H é,í.]=[L kò] sweet=be.NHUM	<i>gá:-Ø.</i> [H gá,] <[L à-Ø]> say.IPFV-3SG
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‘When he (=Pullo) had picked (it) up, opened his mouth wide, and eaten (it), he was saying: “hey, this farmer’s excrement is delicious!”’

<i>nùṅò-bâ:ⁿ</i> <[L nù.ṅò.-]>[H bá,][L à̃] DEM.L-owner	<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.O	<i>bè:-wè-Ø⇒,</i> <[L bè,è.-wè-Ø]> defecate-CAUS.PFV.L-3SG
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<i>nùṅò-bâ:ⁿ</i> <[L nù.ṅò.-]>[H bá,][L à̃] DEM.L-owner	<i>wó</i> [H wó] 3SG.O	<i>ñè:-wⁿè-Ø,</i> <[L ñè,è.-w ⁿ è-Ø]> eat-CAUS.PFV.L-3SG
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‘(So) this one (=Pullo) made him defecate, (and now) this one (=Dogon) made him eat (it).’

<i>sará</i> [H sá.rá] pass.by	<i>gàrà-Ø,</i> <[L gà.rà-Ø]> pass.PFV.L-3SG
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‘It happened (like that).’

<i>kò</i> [L kò] NHUM.S	<i>gàrà-Ø</i> <[H gá.][L rà-Ø]> pass.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM	<i>mà</i> [L mà] POSS	<i>dǎyⁿ,</i> [L dà.][H ý̃] limit
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<i>ìnè</i> <[L ì.nè]> person.L	<i>kó</i> [H kó] NHUM.O	<i>áyà-m</i> <[H á.][L yà,-m]> hear.PFV.HL-PTCP.PL	<i>kâ:ⁿ,</i> [H kǎ,][L à̃] too,	<i>màlfâ:ⁿ</i> [L mà,l.][H fǎ,][L à̃] rifle	<i>ù</i> <[L ù]> 2SG.P	<i>cé=ỹ,</i> [H cé,=][L ý̃] possession=it.is
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‘Ever since (the time) when that happened, (for) people who have (merely) heard it (=the story) too, a rifle belongs to (=is essential for) you-Sg.’

<i>èjú</i> [L è.][H jú] field	<i>mà</i> [L mà] POSS	<i>bèrê:</i> [L bè.][H ré,][L è̃] inside	<i>wár=i:</i> <[H wá.][H r=í,][L ì̃] farming=FOC	<i>wát-tóyò-w,</i> [L wá,][H t.-][H tó.][L yò,-w] farm-IPFV-2SG
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<i>á</i> [H á] 2SG.P	<i>nì:ñé.:</i> [L nì,ì.][H ñé̃] gear	<i>á</i> [H á] 2SG.P	<i>màlfâ:ⁿ .:</i> [L mà,l.][H fǎ,][L à̃] rifle	<i>fú:</i> [H fú,ú] all	<i>dì:ⁿ</i> <[L dǐ,ì̃]> place.L	<i>túmnò,</i> [H tú,m.][L nò̃] single.LOC.HL,
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tèwètè má?
 [L tè.wètè] [H má]
 tag.Q Q

‘In the field(s), if it’s farm work focus that you-Sg are doing, your (regular) gear and your rifle (are) in one place (=together), don’t you find?’

ú é:-rà-bà màlfâ:n kùⁿ é:-w-á:rà-Ø.
 [H ú] [H é,é.-][L rà.-bà] [L mà,l.][H fá,][L à] [L kù] [L è,è.-][H w-á,á,][L rà-Ø]
 2SG.O see-PROG-3PL rifle DEF see-PASS-PROG-3SG

‘They see you-Sg, (and) the rifle is seen (simultaneously).’

kà: wàrù-wára-n lè jà:ⁿ=lá, sàbù
 [L kà,à] <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]> [L lè] <[L jà,à.=]>[H lá] [H sà,][L bù]
 but farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG DAT normal≡NEG because

wàrù-wára-n inè úrò-n=i:
 <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]> <[L ì.nè]> [H ú,][L rò.-][H n=i,][L ì]
 farming.L-farm.H-PTCP.SG person.L bend.over.PFV.HL-PTCP.SG=it.is

inè gàrá: jiré é:-n=i: là:
 <[L ì.nè]> [L gà,][H rá,á] [L jì,][H ré] [H é,é.-][L n=i,ì] [L là,à]
 person.L much(adv) eye see.IPFV-PTCP.SG=it.is NEG

‘But it isn’t normal (=natural) for a farmer, because a farmer is someone who has bent over (and is looking down as he hoes), he is not someone whose eye sees a lot.’

inè úrò-n ké, tòy-i:ⁿ-yáṅá-n
 <[L ì.nè]> [H ú,][L rò,-n] [H ké] <[L tò.y-ì,ì.-]><[H yá.ṅá,-n]>
 person.L bend.over.PFV.HL-PTCP.SG TOP seed-child-look.at-PTCP.SG

èné mà jé:n.: fú: é: dògó bèrè-gò-Ø.
 [L è,][H né] [L mà] [H jé,é,n] [H fú,ú] [H é,é] [L dò,][H gó] <[L bè.rè.-gò-Ø]>
 REFL POSS gear all see finish can-IPFV.NEG.L-3SG

‘One who has bent over, one who looks at the young plants, he cannot completely see (=keep watching) all his gear.’

wàrù-wára yá:-yè-w tán,
 <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá,][L rà]> [L yà,][H á,-][L yè,-w] [H tá,n]
 farming.L-farm.HL go-PFV-2SG if

màlfâ:n lè m̀rⁿó yá:-w dèy,
 [L mà,l.][H fá,][L à] [L lè] [L mò,][H r̀ó] [L yà,][H á,-]<[L w] [L w] <[L w] <[L w] <[L w]
 rifle with come.together go.IPFV-2SG if

dì:ⁿ iné-n fú: kó é:-gò-Ø jín
 <[L d̀,ì,ì]> [H í.né,-n] [H fú,ú] [H kó] <[L è,è.-gò-Ø]> [H jí,n]
 manner.L person-PL all NHUM.O see-IPFV.NEG.L-3SG like

kó bàṅà-rⁿá tí mèyⁿṅ,
 [H kó] [L bà.ṅà.-][H r̀á] [H tí] [L mè,ṅ]

NHUM.O hide-CAUS LINK and

ú inè dì:n kò kò:-Ø
 [H ú] <[L ì.nè]> <[L ðí,ì]> <[L kò]> <[H kó,][L ò-Ø]>
 2SG person.L place.L NHUM.S.L be.NHUM.PFV.HL-PTCP.NHUM

jùgô-n kùⁿ
 [L jù,][H gó,]<[L -n]> [L kù]
 know.IPFV-PTCP.SG DEF

á jé:n lè kó wàγá⇒ dáyá.
 [H á] [H jé,é,n] [L lè] [H kó] [L wà,][H γá] <[H dá.γá]>
 2SG.P gear at NHUM.O far(adv) leave.IMP

‘If you-Sg have gone (to the field) in order to do farm work, if you have gone along with a rifle, having hidden it in a manner (=in a place) that nobody can see it, (then) you-Sg, (namely) the person who knows where it is, leave (imperative) it some distance away from your (other) gear!’

wàrù-wárá-m mà tíⁿíwⁿ bérè yó=kùn.
 <[L wà.rù.-]><[H wá.rá,-n]> [L mà] [H tí.í,ĩ,ĩ] [H bé,][L rè] [H yó,=][L kù,n]
 farming.L-farm.H-PL POSS counsel(n) in exist=be.in.PFV.L

‘That is in (=is part of) the counseling of (=given to) farmers.’

kó nò cín jì:n.
 [H kó] [L nò] [H cí,n] [L jì,ĩ]
 NHUM.S now thus PST

‘It was like that.’

Glosses

Many abbreviations in glosses have been changed compared to (Heath 2008) in order to ensure better compatibility with the Leipzig Glossing Rules, other analytical reports within the current project, or Jeffrey Heath’s subsequent work on Jamsay. Original abbreviations from the grammar are provided in parenthesis.

A – adjective
 CAUS – causative (Caus)
 DAT – dative (Dat)
 DEF – definite determiner (Def)
 DEM – demonstrative (Dem)
 EMPH – emphatic (Emph)
 EXIST – existential (Exist/exist)
 FOC – focus (Foc)
 HORT – hortative (Hort)
 HUM – human
 IMP – imperative (Imprt)
 INTNS – intensifier (Intens)
 IPFV – imperfective (Impf)
 LINK – linking verb (Link)
 LOC – locative (Loc)
 LOG – logophoric pronoun (Logo)
 MSD – masdar/verbal noun (Vb|N)
 N – noun

NEG – negative (Neg)
 NHUM – non-human (Nonh)
 NMLZ — nominalization (Caus)
 O – object pronoun (O)
 P – possessive pronoun (P)
 PASS – passive (Pass)
 PFV – perfective (Perf)
 PL – plural (Pl)
 POSS – possessive particle (Poss)
 Possm – possessum
 Possr – possessor
 Prn – pronoun
 PROG – progressive (Habit)
 PROH – prohibitive (ImprtNeg)
 PST — past (Past)
 PTCP – participle (Ppl)
 PURP – purpose (Purp)
 Q – question particle (Q)
 QuasiV – quasi-verb
 QUOT – quotative (Quot)
 RDP – reduplication (Rdp)
 RECPERF – recent perfect (RecPf)
 RES – resultative (Reslt)
 REV – reversive
 REFL – reflexive pronoun (Refl)
 S – subject pronoun (S)
 SG – singular (Sg)
 TOP – topic (Top)
 V – (1) vowel; (2) verb
 X – item of a variable lexical category

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